

**“Perceptions of Academic Leaders on Various Aspects of
Academic Leadership for Effective Performance of Health
Sciences Institutes”**

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CANDIDATE'S DECLARATION

I, **Dr. Kalidas Dattatraya Chavan** declare that this thesis, entitled “**Perceptions of Academic Leaders on Various Aspects of Academic Leadership for Effective Performance of Health Sciences Institutes**” submitted for the award of the degree of **D.Sc.** of this University, has not been submitted earlier for the award of any Degree or Diploma of this or any other University.

Date: 17.02.2020

Place: Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that this thesis entitled “**Perceptions of Academic Leaders on Various Aspects of Academic Leadership for Effective Performance of Health Sciences Institutes**” has been submitted by **Dr. Kalidas Dattatraya Chavan** for the award of the degree of D.Sc. of Srinivas University.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AYUSH	: Ayurved, Yog, Unani, Siddha and Homoeopathy
CIT	: Communication and Information Technology
DCI	: Dental Council of India
DM	: Doctorate of Medicine
DNB	: Diplomate of National Board
GER	: General Enrolment Rate
INC	: Indian Nursing Council
IT	: Information Technology
MCH	: Magister of Chirurgie
MCI	: Medical Council of India
MD	: Doctor of Medicine
MDS	: Master of Dental Surgery
MS	: Master of Surgery
M.Sc.	: Master of Science
NMC	: National Medical Commission
Ph.D.	: Doctor of Philosophy
Post Doc.	: Post-Doctoral Degree
QAA	: Quality Assurance Agency
REF	: Research Excellence Framework
SPSS	: Statistical Package for Social Sciences
UGC	: University Grants Commission

1.1 Introduction.

"The real role of leadership in education ... is not and should not be command and control. The real role of leadership is climate control, creating a climate of possibility." Ken Robinson. ^[1]

Leadership is defined as the faculty to communicate relentlessly, simplify and be direct with a clear vision, listen, encourage input, model the way and affirm with actions. Presence of strong leadership is a significant element of an effective learning process. A leader is responsible for boom or to plunge into the failure of an institution.

Sincere and dedicated efforts of leaders in the Universities results in organizational growth in future. Influence of academic leaders on various academic activities is noteworthy which may be evaluated in view of their effective output in protecting the welfare of the different stakeholders in the University. Experiences, that a leader has, are multilayered and have various dimensions. They cannot be measured simply as transactional or metamorphic. These experiences are influenced by many components of leaders' lives including social, economical, political, personal and professional factors. Aim of this study is to percept the academic leadership for effective performance of Institutes of Health Sciences as leaders' experiences are important to understand leadership.

1.2 Higher Education in India.

Mr. Jawaharlal Nehru, then prime minister of India has very well elaborated the importance of higher education in India. According to him, the university stands for several reasons including a humanism, tolerance and for quest of ideas as well as search of reality, advancement of human race towards better prosperity. For nation development and wellbeing of the citizens the universities need to discharge their duties satisfactorily". ^[2]

People in different countries, at different points in time, use the term 'Higher Education' in variable ways. This is why the term is ambiguous and does not have a

straight forward definition. Internationally, ‘After school education’ is known as Tertiary Education and can be divided into ‘Higher’ and ‘Further’ education. The higher education in India simply means the post higher secondary education which takes up to three to four years to complete. It was in 1813, the Indian higher education commenced to take its shape in its current form with the renewal of the Charter Act by the then British Parliament, primarily intended at developing education in India, whereby college to impart education in English was established in 1818 at Serampore, Calcutta. ^[2] As a result of these developments, in 1947, there were over 20 universities and 500 affiliated colleges in India. There has been striking development in higher education in India after independence, which is evident from precise facts and figures. India is third largest in terms of size of higher education, after China and The United States. ^[3]

1.3 Health Sciences Education in India.

In India, considering its large population, availability of healthcare human resources is a crucial factor for effective and quality health care delivery. Its role is significant in achieving the goals of national health policy, understanding the importance of goals of millennium development, improving maternal health and reducing child mortality in India. ^[4, 5] In spite having such a key role, the overall scenario about the availability of such healthcare human resource in India is gloomy.

Although the health sciences education in modern days is much improved and technology based, however it can be traced back to the ancient times, when the Charaka and Sushruta had their own doctrines in treating and teaching indigenous system of Medicine in ancient India. ^[6] The establishment of medical science institutions in India for formal training to students was started in British rule, however later on, various other institutions to train the students in health sciences including Ayurveda, Unani, Homeopathy, and Siddha (AYUSH) were established across the country. ^[7] Starting with 28 teaching institutions at the under graduate level at the time of independence, India has reached over 400 medical colleges till now. This includes establishment of several AYUSH institutions across the country.

Due to budgetary constraints and limited infrastructure, it is a challenge for Government of India to meet the overwhelming demand for medical education in the country. ^[8] With time, the private sector entered in the medical education and today,

it contributes to a major portion of the health sciences education in India. Government has established professional councils for controlling and promoting the health sciences education in the country e.g. Medical Council, Dental Council, Nursing Council etc.

1.4 Academic Leadership

In general, distinguishing feature of 'leading' in educational research literature is the ability of an individual or group to influence the "goal-directed behavior of others".^[9] It is seen as "an individual's ability to contribute, to inspire, and enable the effectiveness and success of organizations in which they are members".^[10] Many authors state that the focus is on change, with universities identifying an important role for the 'transformational leader' in the current rapidly changing context.^[11, 12]

Academic leadership involves demonstrating qualities and behaviors, which relate to values and identities within either informal or formal contexts. However, academic management involves allocating tasks and enacting institutional processes usually within a formal context.^[13, 24] Leadership activity is seen as intertwined with management (and administration). Although academic leadership and management are interwoven and complementary and shows 'a symbiotic relationship,^[14] academic leadership has several dimensions as compared to academic management. The higher education leadership activity is vibrant, composite and multidimensional. Ambiguity in the concept of leadership concept may be perceived as researchers tend to document, interpret and analyze the spirit of leadership pertaining to education from multiple angles.

In past few years various researchers have demonstrated the diversity of universities, departments and turbulent environment of higher education. In a resource-hungry, competitive higher education environment, effective academic leadership can be viewed as being the biggest advantage for a university.^[15] In higher education sector, the words of Kouzes and Posner^[16], who in 2002 had stated that; effective leaders understand the people with whom they work, in terms of their roles, the function of their specific jobs and the larger organizational structure, hold completely true, more so in the context of higher education.

In India, the dynamic nature of social and economic policies within the framework of which colleges and universities operate has its influence on the

academic leadership. In order for the academic leaders to be successful, they must be intuitively cognizant of the unique factors that characterize most campus environments.^[17]

In India, higher education has yet not evolved into a fully grown or a mature industry. The higher educational institutions and universities in India share some uniform properties with reference to their organization, yet they are complex and unique entities.

To understand the effectiveness of the institutes and raise the standards in higher education many model have been described by the researchers which include simple structure, the machine bureaucracy, the divisional form and the adhocracy. Each one of these models have its positive and negative approaches by the leaders, hence it is very difficult to say which one is ideal for a specific higher educational institute. Appropriate and effective leadership within this dynamic environment is very challenging. There are limited studies available which are exclusively focussing on leadership in higher education institutions. The available studies mostly focus on the role of the President of the particular college or University.^[18, 19]

Modern academic leaders must be skilled at assessing student needs, conducting complete evaluation of programs and services, and providing aggressive leadership within a more democratic and legal framework.^[20] Challenges of fluctuations in enrolment, increasing costs and budgetary maintenance, developing delivery systems, increased court cases and a host of other concerns have also met the need for effective leadership in higher education.^[21] In new millennium, academic leaders have to face challenges to be effective in strategic planning, revising managerial structures and bringing better management and elasticity to budget processes and staffing patterns. Truly effective leaders are the individuals who are able to control resources in a way that organizes the organization to meet its goals effectively. Success of an organization to perform its tasks, achieve the goals and to relate to other's attitude are some of the parameters to measure the effectiveness of academic leadership.^[23]

The pervasiveness of the notion of leadership has fascinated researchers to interpret, capture and analyse the essence of leadership in higher education from various perspectives. Recent studies not only shed light on the diversity of universities, departments and leaders, but also highlight the constant change, adjustment and turbulent environment of higher education during the past few years.

Effective academic leadership can be seen as one of the greatest benefits a university can have in a resource-hungry, competitive higher education environment. ^[25]

1.5 Role of Academic Leadership in Higher Education

Higher education leadership studies focuses on the academic leadership qualities such as integrity, courage and passion, trustworthiness, consideration, accountability, adaptability, being able to adapt and change regularly, implementing alternative features to develop people and collaborative partnerships, Create a positive and collegium working environment, be both supportive and able to get the necessary support, and be able to positively influence others. ^[26, 27, 28, 29] Debowski and Blake ^[30] have emphasized that academic leaders of teaching and learning need common characteristics to be critical to many leadership roles - for example, developing a collaborative and supportive culture and knowledge among colleagues as well as ability to provide sharing opportunities. Aziz *et.al.*, ^[31] examined the knowledge, skills, and abilities required for department chairs at a large university.

1.6 Challenges of Academic Leadership in Health Sciences Institutes

Leadership qualities in corporate field, military or in Government sector are well established. Though, academic leadership qualities stem from these established leaderships, there are some basic differences between these established leaderships and academic leadership. For example, whereas in military, it is the seniority or the rank that decides the commanding power, in academic leadership, credibility as a scholar plays a major role. Academic leaders have to lead academic organizations, which are composed of scholars. Scholars investigate complex ideas and are inquisitive about the theoretical, empirical, hypothetical or practical issues. Thus, it is but natural that academic leaders are evolved from within the academia. Academic leader has to lead organizations which are expected to create, disseminate and apply knowledge, in addition to performing the conventional organizational tasks of planning, organizing, staffing, and control.

Today's academic leaders are faced with greater challenges, which are due to increased number of student's population and their diversity, steep competitions, higher costs of education, commercialization of education, raised expectations from academic institutions, increasing litigations against universities, need for use of technological advancements in teaching learning methodologies, increasing Government control and scrutiny, external quality audits etc. A time has come to

decide whether the concept of traditional universities needs modifications in order to meet the requirements to develop a nation's creative and intellectual capital in this current century.

To address all those challenges and to further boost the higher education system academic leaders have to play a crucial role. It is important to have effective and capable academic leaders. Their role in increasing the productivity, boosting morale and making essential changes in the higher education is critical.

In order to ensure that the institutions are not only surviving but thriving in new transitional period which is IT enabled, volatile and competitive, this has contributed a significant growth in the complexity and span of what they were expected to do. ^[32] Hence, studying academic leadership is need of time and we must identify the capabilities of academic leaders in Indian context for effective performance.

1.7 The Rationale

Till date there is no agreement on the precise attribute of a successful leader in higher education, even though many studies have recognized it as tangible phenomenon. This presents multiple possibilities for further studies in the concept leadership in higher education. Perceptions of modern day academic leaders about the qualities required for academic excellence are varied. It is required to identify these perceptions to help strengthen the leadership qualities in the area of higher education. This study is planned to identify various perceptions about leadership qualities and factors affecting these perceptions.

There is increased pressure for change in higher education - radical changes in many instances. The per capita fund is underneath the public purse; there is competition; the demand to generate additional income sources has increased; Institutions are more professional and commercial; Students are having more diverse expectations, diverse and coherent about getting worth for money paid; Examples of litigation against universities are increasing rapidly; Government has increased many investigations; and various external quality audits are being enforced. As compared to thirty years ago there is rapid advancement in communication and information technology (CIT) which has made possible new methods and approaches to learning. During last 25 years many things are unfolded in the world which in result raised question about traditional concept of 'university' whether it is suitable in the 21st

century for the progress of social, intellectual and creative capital of the country. Fundamental questions are being raised about whether a university should have a new knowledge and research is far from mainstream; and where learning is primarily to include the transmission of set material using the 'one-size-fits-all' model executed in lecture theatres, tutorials and laboratories on a set schedule operated in the institute's facility in certain theatres is seen.

Academic leaders must play an important role to address all those challenges to promote the higher education system. There is ample evidence of how important the presence of effective and competent leaders is to make necessary changes in productivity, morale and higher education. Leader is essential for any change in academic institute. The complexity and duration of what leaders are hoping to do has increased significantly. Therefore, studying academic leadership is the need of the hour and we must identify the capabilities of academic leaders in the Indian context for effective performance.

From many research studies it has been revealed that leadership is a tangible and noticeable process there are no universal acceptable precise parameters of an effective leader in higher education. Thus there is urgent need and great opportunity to investigate concept of leadership in higher education. Current academic leaders have different perceptions about the educational qualities required for educational excellence. If thinking and perceptions about qualities are identified, it will help to reinforce leadership qualities in academic leaders in the context of higher education. Therefore this study is planned to identify various assumptions about leadership qualities and factors that influence these perceptions.

1.8 Research Question

What is the perception of academic leaders about various leadership qualities in various health sciences institutes?

1.9 Aim and Objectives

Aim

To appraise the perception of academic leaders about various leadership qualities in various health sciences institutes?

Objectives

1. To identify various academic leadership qualities essential for the effective performance by academic leaders.
2. To identify perception of academic leaders about identified academic leadership qualities.
3. To identify various factors influencing the perceptions about these leadership qualities.

2.1 Importance of Academic Leadership.

Gmelch and Burns ^[33] defined academic leadership as an act of building a community of scholars through the empowerment of faculty and staff to set direction and achieve common purposes. Bolden *et.al.* ^[34] adds to this by defining it as a process by which academic values and identities are constructed, communicated and enacted and that this shapes and informs a sense of purpose for individual academics which are operationalized by individuals who do this through self-leadership which is a characteristic of academic staff.

Davidson ^[35] highlighted the constrained culture within which academic leaders have to operate. She argues that an unusual amount of creativity and ingenuity as well as constraint is required for effective academic leadership. Ramsden ^[36] argues that academic leaders have a good knowledge of teaching and research and must provide the means by which their colleagues can perform well. Garrett & Davies ^[37] argue that an academic leader needs to inspire individuals as this empowers them to achieve their personal and the organizations goals.

Bryman ^[38] views academic leadership as an ability to lead a collegial team in a collaborative and empowering way. In terms of understanding academic leadership it is important to bear in mind what motivates academic staff within their roles. In this regards Morgenroth *et.al.* ^[39] argues that the motivating factors are, challenging/interesting work, opportunities for learning/growth and autonomy. This desire for autonomy particularly impacts on how leadership is carried out in Higher Education and drives the need for leaders to behave in a certain way.

The essential reason for defining and discussing academic leadership is to improve the effectiveness of the organization, argues Siddique *et.al.* ^[40] The definition of organizational effectiveness is open to interpretation as it could encompass many things from student success to organizational sustainability both are equally valid but Siddique *et.al.* ^[40] emphasize the student/research success from an academic perspective as being important.

Ramsden ^[36] mentions four central responsibilities of academic leaders. First and foremost is of an academic leader having a vision, defining strategies, action plan and

planning and managing human and financial resources. Second responsibility mentioned by Ramsden is towards academic staff, in which an academic leader should enable, inspire and motivate them. Thirdly they are responsible for recognizing, developing and assessing performance of their own academic staff and lastly they are responsible for learning to lead in their own area and to improve the overall leadership of the institution.

Individual academics, McFarlane ^[41] argues have to serve five distinct ‘masters’ with their students being perceived as the most important, but also their colleagues, their institutions, their profession/discipline and the wider public. This variety of masters leads to confusion as to where, beyond students their priorities lie. He also refers to academics as ‘citizens’ and this implies that they are part of a collective, part of a community of scholars who serve their different communities and that this is a difficult task as priorities change over time and are different from each of the masters.

Middle managers in academic areas such as Deans/Heads of School occupy a very difficult and complex role argue Clegg & McAuley. ^[42] There is a tension between the needs of the institution through their management functions and the more traditional collegiate way of working which is expected of them by the academic community. Smith ^[43] found that the main roles of middle managers are leader, academic manager, and scholar and staff developer. He also found that activities required for management of personnel & resources, and tasks for governance & representation of the department consumed most of the time in addition to time required for quality and students issues. In his research Smith ^[43] found that the most important attributes for Heads was interpersonal skills, vision and communications skills. This activity and responsibility, he argues, is alongside the individual’s own academic work of teaching, researching and academic supervision. Although, as has been argued; this academic work is critical, if the individual is to maintain their own academic credibility. This view of academic credibility as being essential is echoed by Bolden *et.al.* ^[44] who emphasized from their research that academics will only follow leaders who they consider are credible and that credibility is academic credibility.

Bolden *et.al.* ^[45] noted when exploring different pathways to academic leadership that many academics initially resist taking on a leadership role but in time enjoyed the challenges and influences that it offered and many of them chose to remain in academic leadership rather than returning to their pure academic role. Individuals

found that over time their contribution to ‘academic work’ reduced and they moved from teaching and research to facilitation of teaching and research. This shift indicated the move from an ‘academic’ to a ‘leader’ and could be used to reframe the shift from academic to leader in a way which is not frightening and does not undermine the individual’s identity as an academic.

The psychological contract for academic staff is different; argues Watson ^[46] from that discussed previously; he considers that the concept of ‘membership’ is central to the relationship. He describes this as having a range of dimensions from status through legitimate expectations to inescapable obligations and responsibilities all of which the academic expects the leader to deliver. Being part of the academic community is a significant source of satisfaction for an academic. Ameijde *et.al.*, ^[47] point to a perception that academic staff in institutions perceives an on-going struggle between the traditional pluralist culture, academic freedom and the increase in top-down management and leadership practices.

Academics have been found to value ‘collegiality’ defined as involvement in decision making, support for new/young academics, peer support for all academics in the department and a feeling of being part of a community of scholars. Olsen ^[48] argues that this aspect of academic life has declined in recent years but where it exists it is one of the most attractive aspects of academic life and actually contributed to the retention of academics in the profession. Kossuth ^[49] argues that the use of compassionate leadership models would be appropriate in academic life, these models focus on moving from ‘I’ the leader to ‘we’ and take into account the social and emotional wellbeing of all actors in academic life, she argues that this makes for better employees and therefore for better organizations.

There is an on-going tension within the sector between Universities as employers and their role in providing individual academics with the space and facilities to pursue their own scholarly and disciplinary interests.

Bolden *et.al.* ^[13] found that, in general, academics did not value leadership roles; they perceived them to be low status roles which did not contribute to the ‘real’ academic work. In some instances they perceived leadership to be counterproductive. In contrast Siddique ^[40] argues that there are three types of academic leadership, research leadership, educational leadership and administrative leadership, it is

difficult to imagine that academics would not value research and educational leadership as they are the core activities of an academic and to undertake leadership in these areas is core to their role.

Bolden *et.al.* ^[34] also found that academics spoke of the need for vision and it is difficult to know where this vision would actually come from if it does not come from leaders. Lumby ^[50] discusses the paradox of academics displaying hostility to top down leadership but also wanting/needing top down leadership to set the vision and values for the organization as a whole.

Followers will always view their leader from a technical perspective and this is particularly the case in academia, academic credibility is central to respect for any individual in a leadership position however they will also view them from an emotional perspective as engagement is key to success. This is the balance between respecting the intelligence of the individual and feeling emotionally that they are a good person and should therefore be trusted, argues Ramsden. ^[36]

Gmelch & Miskin ^[51] argue strongly that leaders must be capable of critical self-reflection to be able to assess and improve their own practice. As has been highlighted there are those in institutions who are in formal leadership roles but that there are individuals who 'hold' informal leadership roles where other individuals look to them for leadership even though they hold no place in the leadership hierarchy Bolden *et.al.* ^[34] argues that these individuals are very important and influential in the institution and that they are respected for their personal qualities which include being energizing, competent, warm, ethical, an advocate for the group and scholarly. This obviously overlaps with the requirements for formal leaders but stresses that staff value these traits to such an extent that they bestow leadership roles on those who do not formally hold them.

Characteristics of an effective academic leader are difficult to define but it might be easier to discuss what outcomes from effective leadership may look like. In private sector organizations there are fairly standard measures of success such as the profit. In academia there are less clear measures as profit is not an acceptable concept. Institutions are expressly and publically ranked for some of the work they do such as their research through the REF (Research Excellence Framework) and for their teaching through the QAA (Quality Assurance Agency) ratings.

One of the most influential measures of success is the various league tables published largely by the media such as the Guardian, the Sunday times and the Times Higher. These league tables along with the National Student Survey have a very profound effect on an institution particularly when the results do not reflect the institution's perception of itself in relation to its peers.

Failure is observed by Burgoyne *et.al.* ^[52] as a largely political imperative regardless of the success or failure of the Vice Chancellor; measured by whatever combination of results, the Funding Councils would want to use. Ultimately the impact may be the removal of the Vice Chancellor and some other members of the senior management team but there is no history of institutions 'going to the wall' in the way private sector organizations may be impacted as a result of bad leadership. This could, of course, change as a result of changing political imperatives.

In summary there is a distinction between the requirements academics have for formal leadership and what they require from informal leadership and this is summarized in Figure 1: Hanna & Kirilova ^[53]

Figure 1. Important points for the study around the conceptions of academic leadership and of the breadth of academic.

As defined by Fullan ^[54] leadership is “the process of persuasion or example by which an individual (or leadership team) induces a group to pursue objectives held by the leader or shared by the leader and his or her followers”. In order to be effective, leaders need to cultivate trustworthy relationships in order to convince others to follow them. “Leaders establish an atmosphere of trust by their daily actions”. ^[55] Rebores and Walmsley ^[56] described leadership as “a way of life of dedication to the academic community and profession”. According to Owens and Valesky ^[57] leadership is the way how goals are achieved by working through other people, a team. Sheninger ^[58] views an academic leadership as a challenging profession wherein, each day, the leader is required to perform multiple and varied tasks. “Administrators must create a system where all parts interact and run smoothly from transportation to foodservice, to special education to regular instruction”. Glickman ^[59] pointed out that every day the administrators have to conduct multiple meetings to discuss varied issues including those related to disciplinary matters, parental concerns, deficient staff, finding substitutes etc.

Administrators are also required to conduct pre and post conferences with teachers, observe classroom instructions, analyse, interpret and critically analyse those. This involves significant amount of paper work. Administrators also have to be in sync with the ever changing mandates by the states and district authorities. With such countless responsibilities, it was but natural for Marzano *et.al.* ^[55] to comment that “leadership is considered vital to the successful functioning of many aspects of a school,” and for Mason ^[60] to say that “it is the principal who will set the tone for the school”. Similarly, Whitaker *et.al.* ^[61] opined that the actions of an administrator are highly influential, as they play an essential role in the success of a school. Also, Blankstein, Houston, & Cole ^[62] observed that to be effective, school leaders should focus on the best interest of the students and teachers while taking administrative decisions.

Sigford ^[63] is of the opinion that setting the focus and direction of a school is the prime responsibility of a school leader. Similarly, Fiore ^[64] reports that, “school administrators must regularly exhibit positive leadership characteristics,” while they “make literally dozens of decisions daily on a multitude of issues” ^[65]

As per Whitaker *et.al.*, ^[61] effective administration should keep a balance between their style of leadership and teachers’ morale, while they continue to perform

multiple other administrative tasks. “The top management should be conscious of keeping their workers satisfied, because their leadership has great impact on morale”. Schaefer ^[66] highlights the direct correlation between the morale within the school and employee satisfaction. Also, Long ^[67] observed that a teacher’s decision, whether to continue or leave the teaching profession is greatly influenced by the quality of school leadership.

Weale ^[68] studied that 4 out of 10 teachers quit teaching within a year. He also observed that 20% who newly join teaching profession, leave it within 3 years. As per the study conducted by the National Education Association, the percentage of teachers leaving the profession is even higher in urban districts. Similar statistics was observed by Phillips, ^[69] whereby nearly 50% of all those who enter teaching profession get transferred to a new school or quit the profession within first five years.

Furthermore, as reported by Harvey, ^[70] “surveys indicate that teacher satisfaction has declined dramatically in the last five years, on some measures to the lowest level in the last 25 years”. Hence, it was necessary to search for the various attributes of teachers that boost their morale and those traits of academic leaders that best fostered teacher’s morale, so that quality teachers can be recruited and retained.

2.2 Academic Leaders as Change Agents.

2.2.1 Transactional-Transformational Leadership Approach

In the 1970’s, Burns ^[71] investigated on reinforcement of performance (transactional behavior), along with apprehending followers and developing their self-worth and focus (transformational behaviors). They put an emphasis on vision, staff engagement competence, experimentation, credibility, values, and judgment. ^[72]

In terms of transactional leadership, leaders and followers swap needs and facilities to achieve independent goals, or they form a leadership by exchanging positive reinforcement is provided for good performance. ^[73] Some evidence revealed that a charismatic or transformational leadership style might be more associated with the context of education ^[74] or it is suggested that a combination of transformational and transactional styles are efficient for educational setting. ^[75]

Over the past 20 years, the paradigm of transformational leadership and transformational behavior has gained increasing attention. ^[76] Leaders are capable to

transform the fidelities and behaviors of their staff as a result of shared organizational culture. However negative influences might appear; dialogue among staff might be restrained, problem-solving might reduce and people are observed as the cause of the problems. The pressure on people is suggestive of command-and-controls' structures and rules. Theory of transformational leadership is associated with the significance of individual leaders, the charisma, and intellectual stimulation. ^[77] Additionally, if leaders transform leadership to staff, a dynamic connection to the ideas of other is created to enlighten systematic thinkers. A college administrator can play the role of the transformational leader through incorporating a shared vision of change, enabling voices in a cooperative community and reflecting on vision value. ^[78]

Vision

Professionals in context of education are supposed to raise their awareness in terms of clarity and goal. As per McCleskey ^[79] the ability of leader for articulating an educational vision plays a major role to develop constant improvement. Moreover, it is necessary for leaders to be must be the superintendents for all to achieve a vision of success. To work in an educational environment with current educational requirements, university administrators must be transparent in expressing their expectations and vision to support change. Therefore, leaders achieve success if they act as facilitators instead of authoritarians. Furthermore, if leaders consult with other professionals' points of view in developing a vision, it will allow individuals to feel empowered, committed, imaginative, risk-taker, and get involved. Moreover, it is evident that sharing an apparent vision or clear target facilitates understanding by determining and evaluating goals and outcomes appropriately. In addition, Schafer ^[80] restated that, if the purpose and rationale behind decisions are clearly communicated, the probability of achieving success is very high in an educational context. This integrates collaborating with those who have helped to develop the new vision, which leads to change, and allows individuals to find a solution to meet the needs of students or faculty.

Voices

Based on Scott ^[76] effective leadership is defined as a corporation with others instead of making a decision by a one-person. Moreover, Arnold ^[81] has pointed out that in context of higher education effective leaders, guide through team-working in

web-like systems which are non-hierarchical. If a leader makes the decision for the successful final product, he is required to consult with all members involved to identify the individuals who can lead to expertise. Besides, if a leader allows for the team-working environment, a collaborative culture is developed. Professionals can benefit from collaborative environments which play a pivotal role in the effectiveness of a leader. This environment strengthens a professional learning community in which forces team- working and interactions, and fosters individuals to work cooperatively towards a shared vision.

Values

If the levels of team-working and collaboration are high, the overall process and final product of the vision and the value of its outcome will be successful. Based on Odumeru and Ifeanyi ^[82] effective leadership needs reflection. To this end, the professional requires being aware of when to be introspective. In the context of higher education, leaders are required to evaluate the consequence of the shared vision to realize whether it effectively has met student's and/or staff's needs or if the challenges still continue. According to Bass and Avolio, ^[83] it is essential that leaders lead and guide their institutes into the future by reflecting critically and understanding profoundly the organizational culture and values. The reflection over values enables the individual to consider the achieved goal, take into account mission, values or university needs, and skillfully review what might be necessary with the aim of forming or creating a more effective vision in the imminent future.

In relation to this, transformational leadership creates team-building in order to learn from each other, form and reflects on shaping visions and goals. Frequently this type of cooperation and relationship make positive change and increases the effectiveness of professional leadership practices. Moreover, based on Kim ^[84] the transformational model intent to raise capacity development and increase the levels of personal commitment which bring about the extra work and more productively.

Effectively Leading: Other Considerations

Based on a comprehensive review of the literature, the following characteristics of leader behavior which were related to effective leadership in the context of higher education is discussed consecutively including some demonstrations from the existing literature.

Clear Sense of Direction

This characteristic denotes that effective leaders provide clear and transparent direction regarding the paths and vision of their institution. These kinds of leaders are responsible for a strategic leadership of their institution. Wolverton, Ackerman and Holt ^[85] conducted a study on 200 US senior excellent leaders who had been selected as effective leaders. The results of this study revealed that all these leaders shared a common conspicuous characteristic that is they created a shared organizational vision and goals. Furthermore, Benoit and Graham ^[86] investigated about 13 leaders who designated as effective and excellent leaders by their followers, all pointed to the significance of the leaders who shared a common vision.

Treating Academic Staff with Integrity

This characteristic of leader behavior refers to following attributes; being fair to them, having faith in staff, dealing with staff equitably. Bryman ^[87] realized if leaders treated staff equitably and fairly, it would be more probable that leader develops and maintain self-esteem. Therefore, one of a vital set of aspects ineffective leadership is that leaders must be able to deal with staff consistently, fairly, inclusively, and responsively.

Being Trustworthy

This characteristic of leader behavior refers to this requirement that leaders must be reliable, trustworthy with a high level of integrity. This considered as a common theme in the literature of leadership. ^[87] Trocchia & Andrus ^[88] carried out a study to identify the top characteristics of effective leaders working in marketing departments. They found that integrity, honesty, and fairness were the tope characteristic, and moreover, they revealed that fairness is more associated with the components of effective leadership. Comparably, Bryman ^[89] conducted a study to identify the perceptions of staff towards what are the criteria for effective leadership among heads of department in the higher education context. The data obtained from questionnaires which administered to various groups of deans, fellow heads of department and academic staff. The results revealed that there was a relatively high level of agreement between respondent in different groups. The two criteria of trust and integrity were found to be essential characteristics of effective leaders. Since

these characteristics enhance trust and cooperation among members of the organization and ‘displays integrity and moral behavior in all circumstances.

Encouraging Open Communication

Giving opportunity to be involved in making crucial decisions and creating open communication to discuss the issues of concern are important to effective leadership. The literature frequently establishes its importance for academics. It is much more related to the concept of autonomy among academics since they gain the ability to be responsible for their own work. Czech and Forward ^[90] investigated that open communication among faculty and staff led to the effectiveness of their department. Keith and Buckley ^[91] conducted a study to identify distinctive characteristics of leaders among academics, he found that leaders who were open to suggestion and consulted with staff were successful in maintaining of morale among academic leaders.

Acting as a Role Model and Having Credibility

Typically effective leaders serve as role models for their staff, therefore it is essential for leaders forward to establish credibility as academics. Creswell and Brown ^[92] conducted a qualitative study among 33 US academic leaders who had been identified as effective leaders. They recognized several distinct roles that came out of an examining particular participant that the interviewees helped a member of academic staff to develop efficiently. One of these roles was mentorship, which acted as a model for publicizing research activities, sharing knowledge, commenting on others’ work in terms of publishing and funding. Based on Benoit and Graham’s ^[86] research, serving as a role model in leading teaching and research was considered as one of four salient characteristics of the leaders. These findings associated with credibility and role modeling are consistent with Goodall’s ^[93] research who examined citation patterns. She suggested that it is essential for leaders to have credibility and reliability as researchers as guiding research-oriented universities.

2.3 Factors influencing Academic Leadership.

Following five factors are identified, which have influence on the academic leadership:

- Fiscal and people resources.

- Flexibility, creativity and change-capability.
- Responding to competing tensions and remaining relevant.
- Maintaining academic quality.
- Effective strategic leadership.

Except, the factor of ‘maintaining academic quality’, which is mainly associated with a teacher or academic staff; the four other factors can be identified with both, an administrator and a teacher.

Fiscal and people resource issues

Some of the key challenges cited by academic staff, in addition to competing for resources, include recruiting and retaining quality staff, large volume of paperwork, compliance issues, time required to get funds. This was not surprising for Knight & Trowler ^[94] and Ramsden ^[36] as they observed that in the past decade, universities experienced a sharp decline in Government funding and increased monitoring accountabilities. It was a matter of concern that the academic leaders in universities do not have required skill sets to attract funds. Moreover, the academic staff and leaders are not comfortable to shoulder the bureaucratic burden.

For an academic staff, fund acquisition was a key challenge. Similar to the observations by Coaldrake & Stedman ^[95] most of the academics interviewed, echoed their concerns over constrained resources on the background of huge academic workloads and increased requirements of monitoring and reporting.

The need for flexibility, innovation and change-readiness

Barnett ^[96] and Hanna ^[97] observed that being flexible, adaptable and a problem solver in order to “meet the demands of an increasingly complex and dynamic environment” was a big challenge before a university. Marshall ^[98] and Gayle, Tewarie and White ^[99] stressed the need for leadership development to addresses key challenges like “how to gain consensus among constituents that change is needed”. Scott *et.al.*, ^[32] expressed the need to provide assistance to academic leaders in making sense of the continuously and rapidly changing context. There is an ambiguity in the two naturally associated drivers in higher education i.e. educational and commercial. This necessitates an innovative, flexible and brave approach.

Process of discovering and reinterpreting knowledge is uncertain. As per Ramsden, ^[36] academic people are familiar with it and hence they understand change.

However, it is only if they see change and innovation as being genuinely beneficial to their work, that they will accept it. In a study it was found that even greater challenging for the academic leaders was to engage others in change and innovation. Hence, building robust capacity in others to accept and adapt to change was an important dimension of the role of an academic leader.

Marshall,^[98] Scott *et.al.*^[45] and Whitchurch^[100] agreed that the most critical requirement in the present university environment is the ability to deal with topical issues and lead universities through major change. As per Wheatley,^[101] generally, in an academic organization, a leader should ensure that the people should work with the change, instead of relying on a devised system.

Responding to competing tensions and remaining relevant

According to academic leaders responding to competing tensions and remaining relevant are the challenges in an academic organization. Different stakeholders in academic organizations include students, teachers, parents, college and university authorities, Government etc. According to Cooper^[102] there is divergent philosophical differences and relationships between all these stakeholders. This spells complexity for managing universities. There is a difference between managing a university and managing a business. As per Gayle,^[99] if universities are managed in a business-like way, there are bound to be situations of tension, which will be required to be managed by way of strategic clarity, positive relationship and values.

Maintaining academic quality

At times, the academic values in an academic organization are resisted. Ramsden^[36] identified the challenge of achieving a balance between a regulated environment with increased administrative demands and academic quality. The same author in the year 1998, warned that such a resistance should not be underestimated. Efforts should be made to gain shared consent within a culture that so values autonomy and cooperative decision-making.

Strategic leadership

There is a need for change leadership that fosters an innovative, collaborative and impressive culture. Yelder & Codling^[103] stressed the importance of mobilizing people from diverse background in pursuit of common goal. As per an ontological

‘way of being’ approach suggested by Barnett, ^[104] one should not wait for the circumstances to be favorable but to build personal resilience to deal with the existing or fluctuating circumstances.

Hope of engaging others vests largely on a leader’s personal resilience and ethical consistency to model the way positively to others. Cranston, Ehrich & Kimber ^[105] and Dempster & Berry ^[106] have mentioned ethical considerations that are important for inspiring trust.

Issues pertaining to compliance, difficulty in recruiting, retaining and rewarding the staff, huge paperwork, taking tough decisions and budgetary constraints are the major challenges. Middlehurst ^[107] quoted “insufficient departmental autonomy to carry management through”, as one of the key factor in university leadership. As per Gayle *et.al.* ^[99], the structure and culture of a university reflects the perceptions and attitudes of university leaders who are struggling with all these relevant issues.

This chapter presents the structured methods which were adopted for studying the perceptions of academic leaders on various aspects of academic leadership. Based on literature review as well as the contextual challenges of the topic, a number of important features starting from study design to operational definitions for conducting the research and achieving the outcomes are described in this chapter. Research study design is framework of collection and analysis of data in order to syndicate significance to the research purpose with scientific measures is presented. The theoretical structure within which research was steered and outline for the collection, measurement and analysis of data is described in detail subsequently.

3.1 Study Design

The main objective of the study was to describe the perceptions of academic leaders on academic leadership in a given situation, hence the study followed descriptive cross sectional study design. The study was based on quantitative approach in which a survey was administered among a selected sample of academic leaders of health sciences institutes. The attitudes, opinions, behaviors and perceptions of academic leaders were collected. The study was based on primary type of information, the secondary information was collected from literature to strengthen the outcome of the study.

3.2 Study Setting

The study setting was Health Sciences Institutes /Universities offering formal degree programs of various disciplines in the state of Maharashtra including state funded, private and those affiliated to deemed to be universities.

3.3 Study Period: The study was conducted from August, 2019 to December, 2019.

3.4 Study Population

The study population for the current study was the academic leaders in the health sciences institutions serving in different capacities starting from Heads of the

academic departments in a college, Dean/Principals of the colleges and vice chancellors of the universities.

3.5 Sample Size

The study neither intended to test any hypothesis, nor was it interested in calculating any proportion or mean. It was a descriptive study to identify the perceptions about the leadership qualities. So no formal statistical technique was used to calculate the sample size. However, about 15 % of the available academic leaders, as defined in the inclusion criteria, were initially invited to participate in the study. Considering a third of them will drop out and two third will participate, final sample consisted minimum 10 % of the total available academic leaders. There were about 10 deemed to be Universities, one State University and about 398 health science institutes in the state. Vice chancellors of 3 Universities were included in the study. However, 10 % Deans/Principal's and HOD's as mentioned in table were included in the study. Hence, the total sample size for the study was 3 Vice Chancellor, 43 Dean's/Principal's and 416 HOD's.

Table 3.1. Health Sciences Colleges under State and Deemed universities in Maharashtra state.

Discipline	MUHS	Deemed Universities	Total colleges	Total Depts	No. of HOD's	Sample Size	
						HOD's	Dean's
Medical	42	10	52	21	1092	110	6
Dental	29	9	38	9	342	35	4
Ayurved	72	3	75	14	1050	105	8
Unani	6	0	6	14	84	9	1
Homoeopathy	53	1	54	12	648	65	6
Nursing	113	13	126	5	630	63	13
Physiotherapy	42	5	47	6	282	29	5
			398			416	43

3.6 Sampling Technique

The list of all eligible personnel those fit in the definition of academic leaders along with their contact details was collected and compiled from various sources. From this list the required numbers of participants were selected using simple random

sampling technique. Selected participants were invited to participate in the study by sending an online link to fill the survey questionnaire.

3.7 Inclusion Criteria

1. Vice chancellors of the Health Sciences universities
2. Deans of the University / Colleges having at least one Degree Program.
3. Heads of the academic departments of health sciences institutes
4. Ready to participate in the study

3.8 Exclusion Criteria

1. People not working in health sciences institutes
2. Not ready to participate in the study.

3.9 Data Collection Tool

Standard questionnaire developed by Scott *et.al.* ^[32] was employed to operationalize personal capability, interpersonal capability, Intellectual capability, Skill Proficiency and Major areas of Focus in current role, factors influencing academic leadership, Support for Leadership Development, Challenges in academic improvements etc. The data collection tool was modified version based on the extensive review of the relevant literature, which included published scientific report, text books, scientific journals, and other related research materials. The validation of the tool was performed form the experts. The tool was used to obtain relevant information from the leaders. The tool contained questions on the academic leaders academic and career histories and various characteristics of academic leadership as follows

- Personal background of the academic leaders.
- Leadership Capabilities for effective performance including Personal Capabilities, Interpersonal Capabilities, Intellectual Capabilities and Skill Proficiency.
- Major areas of Focus in current role of academic leaders.
- The factors influencing academic leadership role.
- Support for Leadership Development.

- Challenges in academic improvements of institute for effective performance as perceived by academic leaders.

The Likert rating scale was used in questionnaire to obtain the responses on questionnaire items. A Likert survey or rating scale is a parameter that enquires participants to specify their level of agreement with several statements about a particular person, thing, or idea. ^[108]

The data collection from this study provided rich descriptive data that would recognize and describe the academic leadership behaviors that are useful for effective performance of health science institutes. The detail questionnaire for collection of data is presented at the end of the chapter.

3.10 Validation of the Questionnaire

For content validation the questionnaire was first discussed with experts of the field. For further improvement the questionnaire was validated and refined in the light of suggestions of experts. The pilot study was conducted for questionnaire validation where it was administered to ten academic leaders. The necessary modifications after pilot study were then accommodated before actual launch of questionnaire in the study.

3.11 Data Collection

The selected participants after employing simple random sampling strategy were included in the database. The data collection was performed by designing an online questionnaire. The link along with necessary instructions for filling the online questionnaire was sent to the selected participants. The queries of the participants were addressed personally by providing contact number of the investigator. The online window for data collection was kept open for a specific period, when the desired sample size was achieved and all responses were collected the online link was deactivated and the collected data was analyzed.

3.12 Data Analysis

The collected data was analyzed using SPSS. Statistical tests Kendall's W was performed to assess agreement among participants on their perception on various aspects of academic leadership for effective performance in health sciences institutes.

3.13 Operational Definitions

3.13.1 Academic Leadership

Academic leadership is the name given to leadership in an academic setting or organization as a special subdivision of overall leadership. Academic leadership is a leadership that includes such roles as creating vision and mission based on science and research data for the organization, setting up creative ideas, doing and providing teamwork.

3.13.2 Vice Chancellor

The person who is head of the University and responsible for daily academic and administrative affairs of the university.

3.14.3 Dean/Principal

A Person who is controlling authority or is in a leading position in an academic institute offering formal undergraduate program.

3.15.4 Head of the Department

The person who is controlling authority of the academic department in a health science college offering formal academic program.

Chapter IV: Results and Discussion

The study basically intended to understand and explore the perceptions of academic leaders on various aspects of Academic Leadership for Effective Performance of Health Sciences Institutes. The study also tried to highlight strength and limitations of the academic leaders as perceived by them during execution of their current academic role. The overall focus of the study was to identify the leadership characteristics from the academic leaders which will help for effective performance of the health sciences institutions. As described in the methodology the study was categorized in various sub sections starting with personal background of the academic leaders, Leadership Capabilities (including Personal, Interpersonal, Intellectual capabilities and Skills Proficiency), major areas of focus in current role, the factors influencing academic leadership role, support for leadership development and challenges in academic improvements of institute for effective performance as perceived by academic leaders.

This chapter elaborates the interpretation of results and discussion; based on the results obtained to achieve the research objectives and answer the research questions as well as to prove the research hypothesis. Various aspects of academic leadership as perceived by the academic leaders are discussed in view of the various earlier studies and the statistical tests. To support the research outcome and discussion, the findings are also supported by similar studies and research done by other researcher.

For better explanation and understanding of the results this chapter is subdivided under following sub sections.

- 4.1 - Personal background of the academic leaders.
- 4.2 - Leadership Capabilities for effective performance.
- 4.3 - Major areas of Focus in current role of academic leaders.
- 4.4 - The factors influencing academic leadership role.
- 4.5 - Support for Leadership Development.

4.6 - Challenges in academic improvements of institute for effective performance as perceived by academic leaders.

4.7 - Gender wise perceptions of academic leaders on various aspects of academic leadership.

4.8 – Academic qualification wise perceptions of academic leaders on various aspects of academic leadership.

In the subsequent interpretation of the results attempt is being made to understand the exact meaning of results achieved and give an appropriate explanation of the same. After brief review of results and as per the expected outcomes, results are discussed including interpretations that attempt to provide the logical explanation.

As many as 687 respondents had participated in the study, out of which 77.9 % were Head of the Departments, 21.7 % were Dean's/Principals and 0.4 % were Vice Chancellors of the universities. Out of 535 HOD's, 34 % were from Ayurveda discipline followed by 20 % Homoeopathy, 19 % Nursing, 16 % Medical, 6 % Dental and 5.6 % Allied Health Sciences background. Out of 149 Deans, maximum were from Nursing faculty (34.2 %) followed by Allied Health (21.5 %), Ayurveda (19.5 %) Homoeopathy (13.4 %), Dental (6.71 %) and Medical (4.7 %). All three vice chancellors included in the study were from Medical background. Hence, maximum representation in the study in all categories was from Ayurveda background with 31 % respondents followed by Nursing with 22 % respondents, Homoeopathy with 18 % respondents, 14 % from Medical background, 9 % from Allied Health background and remaining 6.1 % from Dental background.

Table 4.1. Discipline wise distribution of respondents.

Discipline	HOD's		Dean's		Vice Chancellors		Total	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Medical	84	16	7	4.7	3	100	94	14
Dental	32	6	10	6.71	-	-	42	6.1
Ayurved	184	34	29	19.5	-	-	213	31
Homoeopathy	105	20	20	13.4	-	-	125	18

Nursing	100	19	51	34.2	-	-	151	22
Allied Health	30	5.6	32	21.5	-	-	62	9
Total	535	100	149	100	3	100	687	100

4.1 Personal background of academic leaders.

The study has received response from 687 academic leaders out of which 318 were females, which is 46.3 % of total respondents and 369 were males, which is 53.7 % of total respondents. This indicates almost equal representation of females at the leadership role in the health sciences institutes across the state of Maharashtra.

An attempt was made to understand the educational qualification of study respondents, it is observed that 79 % academic leaders from present study are holding a post graduate degree i.e. M.Sc./MD/MS/DNB/DM/MCH/MDS and only 21 % academic leaders are holding Ph.D. degree, however none of the academic leader is having post-doctoral degree i.e. PDF or D.Sc.

The distribution of respondents as per their discipline shows that maximum respondents i.e. 31.1 % were from Ayurveda discipline followed by Nursing (22.1 %), Homoeopathy (18.2 %), Modern Medicine (13.4 %), Allied Health (9 %) and Dentistry (6.1 %).

Considering the fact that the outcome of the study will be strongly associated with the current role of academic leaders in the health science institute, it was intended to know the current role of all respondents. The study has received response from 3 (0.4 %) Vice Chancellors, 149 (21.7 %) Deans and 535 (77.9 %) Heads of departments.

It is observed from graph 1 that 30 % respondents from the study were having experience more than 10 years followed by 1-3 years (24.5 %), 4-6 years (19.1 %), 7-10 years (14.1 %) and 12.4 % were having experience under 1 year at their current academic role. This indicates that the perceptions received in the current study are from the mature academic as 63.2 % respondents were having leadership experience of more 4 years and above (Graph 1). This will definitely help to establish a productive conclusion and the study outcome will be indicative of the common perceptions of the academic leaders across the country.

In order to understand the experience of academic leaders which is counted on the basis of number of staff working under the leader, attempt has been made to understand how many persons work under the respondents. It is observed that 62.6 % academic leaders were having less than 10 staff working under them. This is well understood because of the fact that 77.9 % respondent of the study were Head of the Departments where most of the time the staff working are less than 10 only. 27.1 % respondents were having 11-40 staff working under them, this was followed by 5.2 % respondents with 81-120 staff reporting to them and 3.2 % respondents with more than 120 staff reporting to them. This analysis will further help in the study to strengthen the result for better outcome.

4.2 Leadership Capabilities for effective performance.

This section of the chapter elaborates the perceptions of academic leaders about the leadership capabilities for effective performance. An attempt was made to understand the perceptions of leadership capabilities under four categories i.e. Personal capabilities, Interpersonal capabilities, Intellectual capabilities and Skills Proficiency of the academic leaders. The capabilities which are identified in the present study and on which the perceptions are collected from the academic leaders align with the distinguishing attributes of effective higher education leaders. In

present study the academic leaders were asked to rank the given personal capabilities on 1 to 5 scale based on its importance for effective performance in their current role. The ranking assigned by the respondents is presented in subsequent tables and interpretation is done accordingly.

4.2.1 Importance of Personal Capabilities as perceived by academic leader for effective performance

Table 4.2 presents ranking given by academic leaders as perceived by them on five selected personal capabilities for effective performance in health science institutions.

Table 4.2: Ranking by the respondents for various personal capabilities for effective performance in their current role

SI	Personal Capability	Rank 1		Rank 2		Rank 3		Rank 4		Rank 5	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
1	Understanding personal strengths and limitations	221	32.2	147	21.4	137	19.9	93	13.5	89	13.0
2	Being Confident	143	20.8	224	32.6	145	21.1	134	19.5	41	6.0
3	Taking Responsibilities	129	18.8	158	23.0	275	40.0	79	11.5	46	6.7
4	Wanting to achieve the best outcome possible	79	11.5	130	18.9	93	13.5	287	41.8	98	14.3
5	Bouncing back from adversity	115	16.7	28	4.1	37	5.4	94	13.7	413	60.1

Kendall's W = 0.153

Most of the respondents (221 out of 687, 32.2 %) perceived “understanding personal strength and limitations” as the most important personal capability for effective performance in their current role. “Being Confident” was the next important capability as perceived by 32.6 % respondents. 40 % respondents perceived that taking responsibilities during functioning as an academic leader is at the third position for effective performance. Wanting to achieve the best outcome possible was ranked at fourth level by 41.8 % respondents and 60.1 % respondents perceived that bouncing back from adversity is less important personal capability for effective

performance in their current role. Kendall's W was 0.153, signifying the less degree of agreement amongst the participants.

At certain times, the leaders should be able to first manage their own emotional reactions to the uncertainty and discomfort. Here from leaders perspective priority must be to control and manage their self-emotional reaction to the uncertainty and discomfort. ^[32] This helps in not to overreact, to tolerate the uncertainty and to be able to remain calm to perform the leadership role effectively. Problem solving ability is an important attitude to have a high level of interpersonal competence for better understand present situation and to sort out what is the best option to resolve the situation. Both personal and interpersonal capabilities have been expansively researched over the past decade by people like Goleman ^[109] and are often referred to as a leader's 'emotional intelligence'.

According to Scott *et.al.* ^[32], capability is the point of talent; gift or capacity requires producing a lively result and distributing uniqueness under tough, indecisive, continually changing human and industrial situations. They believed that, having this plane of talent and capacity is essential to function effectively with others to attain continuous enhancement and originality.

In a study of academic leadership capabilities of teachers conducted in Myanmar the highest responses in the current personal capabilities of the respondents were received on having energy, passion and enthusiasm for learning and teaching (mean of 4.22). The second highest current personal capability is on maintaining a good work/life balance and keeping things in perspective (4.31) and being bound by a school's code of ethics (4.36). ^[110]

Having energy, passion and enthusiasm for learning and teaching was ranked 1 with mean of 4.7 and wanting to achieve the best outcome possible was ranked 2 by the respondent from the study conducted by Majid Ghasemy. ^[111] However, in the same study Understanding personal strengths and limitations was ranked at number 3 by the academic leaders. These difference in the ranking may be the outcome of the contextual framework of higher education in different countries.

In present study academic leaders have certainly believed that those personal capacities as discussed above are required to perform effectively in the academic setup of health sciences institutes.

4.2.2 Importance of Interpersonal Capabilities as perceived by academic leader for effective performance

The perception of academic leaders about importance of interpersonal capabilities is presented in table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Rankings by the participants for various interpersonal capabilities for effective performance in their current role

SI	Interpersonal Capability	Rank 1		Rank 2		Rank 3		Rank 4		Rank 5	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
1	Being transparent and honest in dealing with others	296	43.1	116	16.9	86	12.5	74	10.8	115	16.7
2	Motivating others to achieve goals	87	12.7	212	30.9	144	21.0	154	22.4	90	13.1
3	Developing and contributing positively in team based programs	95	13.8	130	18.9	239	34.8	133	19.4	90	13.1
4	Listening to different point of views before coming to decision	85	12.4	159	23.1	136	19.8	197	28.7	110	16.0
5	Empathizing and working positively with staff	124	18.0	70	10.2	82	11.9	129	18.8	282	41.0

Kendall's W = 0.067

Most of the participants (296 out of 687, 43.1%) perceived “Being transparent and honest in dealing with others” as the most important interpersonal capability for effective performance in their current role. “Empathizing and working positively with staff” was the next important capability, as perceived by 30.9 % respondents. 34.8 % respondents ranked developing and contributing positively in team based programs on third number followed by Listening to different point of views before coming to decision at fourth number by 28.7 % respondents. 41 % respondents perceived that Empathizing and working positively with staff has got least priority on five point scale as an interpersonal capability for effective performance. However the Kendall's W was 0.067, signifying the less degree of agreement amongst the participants.

The outcome of the study is similar to the study conducted by Majid Ghasemy [111] as a doctoral research on Capabilities and Competencies Related to Leadership

Performance Effectiveness in the Context of Change in Malaysian Higher Education Institutions. The study was conducted on 12 point scale. He reported that being transparent and honest in dealings with others was rated first rank by the respondents with the mean of 4.7. Similarly, motivating others to achieve positive outcomes was ranked second with mean of 4.6. Developing and contributing positively to team-based program was ranked 4 with mean of 4.9. Listening to different points of view before coming to a decision was ranked at third and Empathizing and working productively with staff and other key players from a wide range of backgrounds was ranked at seventh. As discussed in earlier section, these variation in the ranking for various parameters may be because of the differences in contextual frameworks of higher educational policies. However, most of the findings of present study are similar to the findings of Majid Ghasemy. ^[111]

4.2.3 Importance of Intellectual Capabilities as perceived by academic leader for effective performance

The perception of academic leaders on Interpersonal Capabilities of academic leader for effective performance is shown in table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Ranking by the respondents for various intellectual capabilities for effective performance in their current role

SI	Intellectual Capability	Rank 1		Rank 2		Rank 3		Rank 4		Rank 5	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
1	Thinking creatively and laterally	233	33.9	175	25.5	96	14.0	77	11.2	106	15.4
2	Setting and justifying priorities of work	223	32.5	211	30.7	98	14.3	104	15.1	51	7.4
3	Making sense of learning from experiences	69	10.0	101	14.7	294	42.8	123	17.9	100	14.6
4	Adjusting plan of action in response to the problems encountered while implementing.	60	8.7	129	18.8	126	18.3	256	37.3	116	16.9
5	Assessing the likely outcome of course of action.	102	14.8	71	10.3	73	10.6	127	18.5	314	45.7

Kendall's W =0.13

About 233 out of 687 (33.9%) respondents perceived “Thinking creatively and laterally” as the most important intellectual capability for effective performance in their current role. “Setting and justifying priorities of work” was also ranked one as important capability, as perceived by 32.5 % respondents. 42.8 % respondents perceived that making sense of learning from experiences is the third important capability for effective performance as an academic leader. Adjusting plan of action in response to the problems encountered while implementing was given fourth rank by maximum respondents i.e. 37.3 % and Assessing the likely outcome of course of action was perceived as least important intellectual capability by 45.7 % respondents. Kendall’s W was 0.13, signifying the less degree of agreement amongst the participants.

In present study the focus on capabilities has meant that particular attention has been given to developing the ‘insider’s view’ on how the 687 experienced academic leaders who participated in the study respond to, think their way through, and resolve the key challenges and dilemmas associated with each of the roles investigated; along with how they learn and develop in each role. It is the application of one’s emotional intelligence and intellectual capabilities to determine when and when not to deploy them that make the difference. It is a focus that, therefore, looks at leadership in context and from the inside out, not just from the outside in. ^[32]

In the study conducted by Mary Jacqueline and Kanog-on Rungrojngarmcharoen, ^[110] on academic leadership capabilities of teachers in a selected no. 2 basic education high school in Myanmar, they reported highest current cognitive capability of the respondents is on learning from experience (mean of 4.27). The second highest current cognitive capability they reported is setting priorities for their daily work (3.96). The third highest current cognitive capabilities are having a clear justified and using previous experience to figure out what’s going on when a current situation tasks an unexpected turn (3.84).

However, Majid Ghasemy, ^[111] have reported that thinking creatively and laterally was ranked at 3 by the respondents and Setting and justifying priorities for daily work was ranked at 5. Making sense of and learning from experience was ranked at 5 and adjusting a plan of action in response to problems that are identified during its implementation was ranked at 13. Hence, the findings of the present study are quite similar to that of the results reported by Majid Ghasemy. ^[111]

4.2.4 Importance of Skill Proficiency as perceived by academic leaders for effective performance

The perception of academic leaders on the Importance of Skill for effective performance in health science institutes is presented in table 4.5.

Table 4.5: Ranking by the respondents for various skills for effective performance in their current role

SI	Skills Proficiency	Rank 1		Rank 2		Rank 3		Rank 4		Rank 5	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
1	Skill to implement a new educational program effectively	245	35.7	124	18.0	106	15.4	96	14.0	116	16.9
2	Being able to use Information Communication technology	113	16.4	184	26.8	133	19.4	153	22.3	104	15.1
3	Ability to chair meetings effectively	95	13.8	122	17.8	215	31.3	126	18.3	129	18.8
4	Ability to develop policy documents	83	12.1	155	22.6	125	18.2	202	29.4	122	17.8
5	Skills of resource management.	151	22.0	102	14.8	108	15.7	110	16.0	216	31.4

Kendall's W =0.0263

About 245 out of 687 (35.7 %) respondents perceived “Skill to implement a new educational program effectively” as the most important skill for effective performance in their current role. “Skills of resource management” was the next important skill, as perceived by 26.8 % respondents. 31.3 % respondents perceived that Ability to chair meetings effectively is third important Skills Proficiency required for effective performance in health science institutes. Ability to develop policy documents was recognized as fourth important skill proficiency by 29.4 % respondents followed by 31.4 % respondents who perceived Skills of resource management is the least important skill proficiency required for effective performance. Kendall's W was 0.0263, signifying the less degree of agreement amongst the participants.

As per Elham Shahmandi, ^[112] today's leaders need to know new knowledge, abilities and skills to effectively cope with the constant organizational changes. During the process of acquiring educational qualification, it is desired that the management school will significantly influence management practice when it becomes capable of teaching a specific set of "skills" associated with the job of managing". ^[113]

Being able to use IT effectively to communicate and perform key work functions was ranked 7 by the respondents in the study conducted by Majid Ghasemy. ^[111]. This was ranked 2 in the present study. An ability to chair meetings effectively was ranked 3 in the same study and Having sound administrative and resource management skills was ranked 4. Hence, most of the findings of the study are in conformity with the study conducted by Majid Ghasemy. ^[111]

4.3 Major areas of Focus in current role of academic leaders.

The respondents were asked to rank the given parameters/areas or activities according to its importance to deliver their portfolio. The rank was on 1 to 10 scale in the ascending order of importance of that particular parameter.

Table 4.6: Ranking by the respondents for major areas of focus in their current role

Major area of focus	Rank									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Managing the Relationship with the staff	183	69	57	51	59	55	32	41	57	83
Staff Development	42	166	87	81	63	66	54	63	47	18
College/University Development	71	71	144	81	76	55	61	44	39	45
Performance Appraisal of Staff	27	53	74	140	74	64	77	59	54	65
Strategic Planning for College/University Development	77	69	70	73	172	74	56	50	27	19
Special attention to College/University Academic Development	54	65	71	80	69	155	66	58	41	28
Institutional Research	25	30	48	61	47	80	166	88	84	58

Compliance of council requirement (UGC/NMC/MCI/DCI/INC etc)	37	39	65	42	38	43	62	157	106	98
Students welfare	77	71	41	46	48	47	64	65	159	69
General Administration and Discipline	93	54	31	33	42	47	48	61	73	205

Kendall's W = 0.0281

Although the academic leaders at different positions are expected to focus on several assignments at a time, it is likely that they will prioritize their task and execute accordingly. In the present study, about 183 out of 687 (26.64 %) said that “Managing the Relationship with the staff” as the major area of focus in their current role. “Staff Development” was the next important focus, as perceived by the participants. 21 % participants perceived that College or University Development is third important thing for them for delivering their portfolio.

In spite of the fact that it is important, performance Appraisal of Staff was given fourth rank by 20.4 % respondents. Strategic Planning for College/ University Development was given fifth rank by most of the respondents i.e. 25 %, Special attention to College/University Academic Development was given sixth rank by 22.6 % respondents, Institutional Research was placed at seventh position by 24.2 %, Compliance of council requirement (UGC/NMC/MCI/DCI/INC etc) was perceived as eight important parameter for delivering the portfolio by 22.9 % respondents, students welfare was placed at ninth place by 23.1 % respondents and General Administration and Discipline was perceived as the least important thing by 29.8 % respondents as compared to other parameter under study. Kendall's W was 0.0281, signifying the less degree of agreement amongst the participants.

Managing the relationship with the staff is an art which effectively monitors and manages the relation between individuals and it helps in strengthening the bond among the employees and ensures that each one is contented and enjoys a healthy relation with each other. If the staff feels in relation to their jobs and work place, they will have job satisfaction. ^[114] This could be the reason for ranking this parameter at the top by the academic leaders of present study.

There is an emerging consensus among educational policy makers, researchers and practitioners that teacher professional development is vitally important to

educational reform as we approach the next millennium. ^[115] On the same lines, the respondents of the present study have rated staff development as an important focus of delivering their portfolio.

Many researchers have demonstrated that merely 3% of universities and colleges invest in developing their academic leaders – deans and department chairs. We need to do emphasis into the development of academic leaders which may shed some light to help illuminate the way to the Building Age of our leadership capacity in colleges and universities. ^[116] On the other hand the role of academic leaders in university and college development is equally important. As Indian universities have been facing number of challenges for enlisting world-class status so a very few Indian higher educational institutions have listed in the global rankings system. ^[117] One major reason for this could be the lack of academic leader’s contribution towards college and university development. Hence, this has been ranked as an important area of focus by respondents in present study.

In institutions of higher education performance appraisal of academics has not received enough attention from, policymakers and administrators of tertiary institutions in the past, hence, its contribution to enhance institutional performance and quality appear to have been neglected. ^[118]

4.4 The factors influencing academic leadership role.

Similarly as any other managers or leaders, academic leaders also come across the situation where combination of factors influences their role. Hence, the academic leaders are expected to perform good exercise in order to justify their role in deciding policies or procedure for the health sciences institutes. The respondents were asked to rank the level of impact that each of the given parameter has on their daily work. The ranking was on one to ten scale on the basis of its impact in ascending order. Table 4.7 illustrates the results in the form of ranking assigned by the academic leaders for ten given parameters.

Table 4.7: Factors influencing current role of academic leaders.

Factors influencing current role	Rank									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Role of the Government (and its agencies)	159	84	58	35	51	45	43	52	53	107

Council Regulations and guidelines	116	165	69	48	41	48	47	40	90	23
Growing competition (Local and International)	47	61	132	74	67	52	67	93	48	46
Finding and retaining high quality staff	113	76	94	125	63	51	66	31	35	33
Financial Management	34	64	75	88	145	113	54	40	42	32
Maintaining specific institutional Image	40	40	67	97	109	159	66	44	37	28
Administrative pressure from sponsoring body/trust	32	34	50	91	57	59	153	77	81	53
Increased student diversity	31	48	74	49	67	61	85	150	70	52
Pressure of completing enrollment/admissions	39	60	36	41	32	50	59	95	163	112
Declining quality of academic and research	77	55	32	39	54	49	45	64	72	200

Kendall's W = 0.009

Influence is a significant concept for leaders, without it there would be no change. Influence is the key in organizations with shared or distributes leadership processes in place. ^[119] Leadership in academic setup is affected by several factors. Perceptions of academic leaders are discussed below.

About 159 out of 687 (i.e. 23.1%) respondents said that “Role of the Government (and its agencies)” as the major factor influencing their current role. “General Council Regulations and guidelines” was the next important influencing factor, as perceived by 24 % respondents. 19.2 % respondents of the study perceived Growing competition (Local and International) as the third important factor which has influence on their day to day activities. The problems with finding as well as retaining high quality staff was also perceived as important challenge by academic leaders. Around 18.2 % respondents opined that they face difficulty in managing good quality staff. Financial Management of the organization has been rated as fourth major influencing factor by the academic leaders. 21.1 respondents reported that they get difficulty in financial management of the organization which influences their

portfolio. Social Image of the academic institutions has been always remained a challenge, 23.1 % respondents have perceived this as an important influencing factor while delivering their portfolio. Health sciences institutes always have to perform an exercise of balancing the sponsoring trust/body and the academic institutes, when asked about it as a challenge, 22.3 % responded that they have huge administrative pressure from sponsoring body which influences their leadership role. Pressure of completing enrollment/admissions in the academic institutions was perceived as an influencing factor by 23.7% respondents and placed at ninth rank. In India the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) for higher education is 15% which is relatively low as compared to the developed as well as, other developing countries. Declining quality of academics and research was given last rank by 29.1 % respondents. Kendall's W was 0.009 for this parameter, signifying the less degree of agreement amongst the participants.

It is evident from the fact that, the government policies in recent past have influenced the higher education and the academic leaders there off. This is because of the uncertainty created by the policy makers on various aspects of higher education reforms. For any country the economic, political, social, and academic benefits associated with the internationalization of higher education so it is broadly considered as a planned priority for governments around the world. ^[120] hence, government is focusing on a major shift in higher education which might have influenced the role of academic leaders in Indian context.

Increased student diversity was assigned eighth rank by most of the participant's i.e. 21.8 % in the study. Scott *et.al.* ^[32] have also reported the influence by student diversity on the leadership role. The academic leaders including Dean, Head of the dept. and Vice chancellors from their study have also indicated that diversity in the students affects the leadership role in higher education. The results are in agreement with Guthrie, ^[121] who reported that the biggest challenge for colleges and academic leaders is to educate a more diverse set of students from a wider range of backgrounds.

In India there is increase of enrolments at school level, but the number of higher education institutes are inadequate so insufficient to meet the growing demand. ^[122] Although the overall enrollment in higher education is less as compare to that of pre higher education, there is always a pressure on the academic leaders to fill the

total strength of students and hence, the respondents might have opined it as a challenge.

The leadership qualities also includes research as an important component, however producing research outcome has been also considered as a major challenge by the academic leaders as mentioned in the earlier studies. ^[123]

4.5 Support for Leadership Development.

Academic leadership is based on the leadership capabilities earned by the leaders. It is basically a combination of factors which support the development of leaders. The respondents of the study were asked to give their perception on effectiveness of given activities/parameters in developing their capabilities as an academic leader. Ten activities were given and the respondents were asked to give the ranking on the scale of 1 to 10 in ascending order of its importance or effectiveness. Table 4.8 presents results and perceptions of respondents on given parameters.

Table 4.8: Factors supporting leadership development of Academic Leaders.

Factors Supporting Leadership	Rank									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Completing a tertiary qualification relevant to leadership	139	64	49	35	41	48	43	49	78	141
Participating higher education leadership seminars	94	152	52	53	58	44	53	61	100	20
Accessing leadership information on internet.	28	54	111	54	48	60	64	113	65	90
Completing formal leadership program	35	31	67	133	58	68	117	71	68	39
Participating in the quality assurance activities of the college/university	98	59	74	68	146	110	47	35	20	30
Undertaking self-guided reading on leadership	54	49	50	78	104	154	62	48	41	47
Involvement of professional leadership	41	57	70	113	73	62	139	57	58	17

groups/associations											
Learning opportunities during peer group discussion	32	82	111	50	64	46	57	149	66	30	
Attending learning and teaching conference	75	97	65	54	49	61	56	56	119	55	
Being involved in informal mentoring/coaching	91	42	38	49	46	34	50	47	71	219	

Kendall's W=0.004

This academic leadership development program aims at providing faculty leaders with tools and skills to navigate the myriad of issues encountered in leadership roles as academic leadership is unquestionably a critical component in striving for excellence of academic institutions. Academic leadership qualities are not compatible with institutional purposes, cultures and expectations as compared with exercise of leadership of typical business leader. ^[124] The parameters supporting academic leadership as perceived by academic leaders are discussed below.

About 139 out of 687 (i.e. 20.2 %) respondents said that “Completing a tertiary qualification relevant to leadership” as the most important support for leadership development. “Participating in the quality assurance activities of the college/ university” was the next important supporting factor, as perceived by the 22.1 respondents. Internet being a source of getting huge leadership information has been assigned at third rank by 16.2 % respondents of the study. The coaching and learning through formal leadership programs have been recognized as fourth important supportive activity for leadership development by the respondents.

Taking active participation in the quality assurance activities of the college/university has been perceived as fifth important and supportive activity for leadership development by the academic leaders from the study. 22.4 % leaders have opined that undertaking self-guided reading on leadership is supportive in leadership development and has been ranked at number six. Involvement of professional leadership groups/associations was given seventh rank by 20.2 % and learning opportunities during peer group discussion was given eighth rank and 21.7 % respondents opined that it also supports in leadership development. Attending learning and teaching conference and Being involved in informal mentoring/coaching were assigned ninth and tenth rank by 17.3 % and 31.9 % respondents respectively.

Kendall's W was 0.004, signifying the less degree of agreement amongst the participants.

The findings of qualification as supporting parameter for leadership development are similar to a previous study in which Khan ^[125] explored that the heads with higher professional qualifications are more efficient. However, findings are contradictory with few studies which reported that highest academic credentials e.g. (Up to Graduation's Up to Master's and Above Master's) did not influence leadership style. ^[126, 127]

It is discussed on every platform that the leadership plays key role in quality assurance effort. Higher education institution needs to be led by leader who can apply his leadership effectively. ^[128] According to Omolayo, ^[129] the role of leaders of higher education institution is essential because leaders look for voluntary participation of their subordinates in order to achieve the goals of organization. This might be the reason for ranking this parameter at second place by the respondents in present study.

Practicing ICT for leadership development in the developmental organizations is very common in modern days. Information Technology through digitalization and the digital transformation is quickly and basically altering current businesses and organizations alike. ^[130] Hence, the academic leaders have also perceived that accessing the leadership development information on internet has helped them to support their leadership role

In the past few years, coaching has been increasingly found as the one type of leadership development intervention that is gaining importance and popularity. ^[131, 132] Coaching has potential to offer a higher level of psychological safety than all other leadership development programs. It also allows for working on an established plan. Hence, the respondents of the present study might have ranked coaching through formal leadership program as an important supportive factor for their leadership development.

4.6 Challenges in academic improvement of institute for effective performance as perceived by academic leaders.

Every academic institute goes through the hard phases of development where certain factors or challenges act against the academic improvement of the institute for effective performance. The attempt was made to collect the perceptions of the academic leaders as how they perceive different challenges and hurdles in academic improvement of institute. 10 most common challenges/hurdles were given as an option and the respondents were asked to rank them on the scale of 1 to 10 in ascending order of challenge. Table 4.9 presents the results as perceived by the respondents.

Table 4.9: Challenges / Hurdles in academic improvement of Institute

Challenges / Hurdles	Rank									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Management/ Government policies	217	68	47	48	48	57	42	55	44	61
Lack of timely and sufficient financial assistance	98	167	76	50	54	45	51	54	59	33
Frequently changing guidelines by regulatory authorities	54	106	168	69	69	41	50	68	34	28
Difficulty in getting/ retaining/ managing teaching staff	76	74	84	163	61	53	85	32	22	37
Multiple Reporting protocols (to Government / other authorities)	21	46	75	76	178	127	51	42	49	22
Time consumed by non-academic activities	64	55	58	75	102	163	69	49	30	22
Students activities affecting academics	25	41	58	73	63	78	186	80	51	32
Local political issues	37	36	48	35	23	28	58	158	118	146
Difficulties in promoting quality research	39	67	49	54	52	55	54	99	172	46
Difficulties in attracting foreign university collaborations	57	27	25	43	36	39	40	51	108	261

Kendall's W = 0.134

In terms of students next to China and the United States, Indian Higher Education system is at third rank in the world. In order to compete in global economy, India is striving in the areas that require highly trained professionals and in this situation the quality of higher education becomes increasingly important. ^[133] Hence, the challenges for academic leaders for improvement in higher education system becomes important.

Most of the participants, 217 (i.e. 31.6 %) respondents perceived “Management/ Government policies” as the challenge / hurdle in academic leadership development. “Lack of timely and sufficient financial assistance” was the next important challenge/hurdle, as perceived by 24.3 % respondents. Most of the participants felt that frequently changing guidelines by regulatory authorities is most important challenge in academic improvement of institute for effective performance and this was ranked third by 24.5 % participants. Difficulty in getting/ retaining/ managing teaching staff was perceived as an important hurdle by 23.7 % respondents and was placed at fourth place. Multiple Reporting protocols (to Government / other authorities) was placed at fifth level and 25.9 % respondents felt that it is also one of the major challenges in academic improvement of the institute. Total time consumed by the non-academic activities was perceived as a hurdle by 23.7 % respondent and was placed at sixth place in the rank. 27.1 % respondents felt that Students activities affecting academics is also a challenge. Local political issues was placed at eighth place by 23 % respondents.

Difficulties in promoting quality research and difficulties in attracting foreign university collaborations was placed at ninth and tenth position by 25 % and 38.5 % respondents respectively. Kendall’s W was 0.134, signifying the fair degree of agreement amongst the participants.

The financial behavior of the higher education is one of the most complex phenomenon. Higher education has been receiving a decreasing share of the public purse since last 30 years even though accelerating rate of the Great Recession. ^[135] There is need of understanding regarding financing of higher education ac in terms of its historical pattern, projection for the future and assess in what direction higher education system is likely to move. ^[134] Hence, for all higher education institutes, continuous financial support has been always a big question. The academic leaders

therefore rightly raised the concern about lack of timely and sufficient financial assistance as a challenge for academic improvement of institute.

In recent past it has been observed that the retaining teaching staff is the most difficult challenge in all higher educational institutes. Due to inadequate number of faculties and failure to attract and retain qualified teachers by state educational system are the main challenges to deliver quality education.^[133]

Higher education institutes are not unable to focus on research in addition there is shortage of resources and facilities and inadequate quality faculty to mentor students. Most important issue of research scholars are either not receiving fellowships in time or working without fellowships which is hampering the quality of research in higher education. Lack of networking in higher education institutions and research centers is perceived by the respondents in current study.^[133] Another reason for research promotion becomes difficult could be managing the research talent by Indian academic institutions. Challenges like Professors of University are opting option of job in Industry not only for money but also to have access to adequate resources and support data to investigate interesting problems. On the other hand even leading research Universities are unable to recruit top research talent.^[121] Colleges and universities are working hard among themselves to engage collaboratively with other universities and private enterprise in order to get access to big data and participate to be at the advance research and discovery. However, the foreign universities are not willing to come forward and hence the respondents form present study might have perceived this as a hurdle in the academic improvement of the institute.

4.7 Gender wise perceptions of academic leaders on various aspects of academic leadership.

It is intended, under this section, to investigate if the leader's gender influences the way they perceive given leadership quality, which invariably tends to influence performance or allegiance to that leader. The respondents were to indicate their level of importance to the variable on 1 to 5 scale for leadership capabilities and 1 to 10 scale for all other parameters.

It has been often discussed that women are not equally distributed to that of men at the leadership positions. Researchers have noticed that women are indeed still underrepresented in positions of leadership and women are indeed still experiencing gendered discrimination. ^[136]

It is observed that participation of qualified women is very low in the leadership positions even though there are more than enough qualified women to fill available leadership positions. It is reported that women now earned the majority of all college degrees and are well represented in entry- and mid-level positions in most economic sectors, they have surprisingly low progress in achieving post of chief executive anywhere, including in higher education. ^[137]

Gender differences in leadership styles have been the most intensely studied topics in the field of leadership in past two decades.

Are there inherent differences in the way men and women function as leaders and, if so, are these differences gender linked? This question has commanded attention because researchers have been trying to provide an explanation about why there have been so few women leaders. Even though women have become an increasingly large proportion of the work force, they still do not hold a proportionate share of the top administrative positions. ^[138]

In present study it has been reported that out of 687 respondents 318 were females which is 46.3 % of total respondents. Hence, the representation of women in academic leadership position is almost equal to that of men. Although the representation of both men and women is same in the study, an attempt was made to logically establish any variations in the perceptions based on the gender differences as achieved in the study results.

For better understanding this section is discussed and divide under following subheadings.

4.7.1- Gender and Leadership Capabilities for effective performance.

4.7.2- Gender and Major Areas of Focus in current role of academic leaders.

4.7.3- Gender and The factors influencing academic leadership role.

4.7.4- Gender and the factors supporting academic leadership role.

4.7.5- Gender and challenges / hurdles in academic improvement.

Table 4.10: Gender-wise ranking by the participants for Leadership Capabilities for effective performance in their current role.

Leadership Capabilities		Ranking by Male (369)					Ranking by Female (318)				
		1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
Personal Capabilities	Understanding personal strengths and limitations	124	80	58	32	75	97	63	71	47	40
	Being Confident	83	118	73	80	15	64	106	85	50	13
	Taking Responsibilities	62	70	169	50	18	75	75	106	43	19
	Wanting to achieve the best outcome possible	44	81	45	152	47	49	53	34	135	47
	Bouncing back from adversity	56	20	24	55	214	33	21	22	43	199
Kendall W = 0.128						Kendall W = 0.189					
Interpersonal Capabilities	Being transparent and honest in dealing with others	165	50	34	48	72	131	37	61	37	52
	Motivating others to achieve goals	64	118	78	78	31	52	94	52	81	39
	Developing and contributing positively in team based programs	42	73	136	79	39	44	71	103	57	43
	Listening to different point of views before coming to decision	39	76	72	112	70	35	78	61	85	59
	Empathizing and working positively with staff	59	52	49	52	157	56	38	41	58	125
Kendall W = 0.076						Kendall W = 0.058					

Intellectual Capabilities	Thinking creatively and laterally	127	99	46	36	61	106	124	23	24	41
	Setting and justifying priorities of work	91	116	50	70	42	84	95	51	59	29
	Making sense of learning from experiences	44	64	164	59	38	52	34	130	67	35
	Adjusting plan of action in response to the problems encountered while implementing.	42	58	56	144	69	35	46	67	112	58
	Assessing the likely outcome of course of action.	65	32	53	60	159	41	19	47	56	155
		Kendall W = 0.097					Kendall W = 0.181				
Skills	Skill to implement a new educational program effectively	133	62	49	44	81	112	51	46	39	70
	Being able to use Information Communication technology	63	104	62	86	54	61	80	60	69	48
	Ability to chair meetings effectively	49	64	130	66	60	57	69	85	59	48
	Ability to develop policy documents	52	86	68	115	48	44	67	58	87	62
	Skills of resource management.	72	53	60	58	126	44	51	69	64	90
		Kendall W = 0.022					Kendall W = 0.032				

Table 4.11: Gender-wise rankings by the participants for major areas of focus in their current role.

Major areas of focus	Male										Female									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Managing Relationship with staff	95	30	33	16	37	28	18	21	11	18	88	12	38	11	40	26	7	16	15	8
Staff Development	39	94	43	27	32	31	19	22	8	5	30	72	28	26	37	34	11	17	6	12
College/University Development	33	42	92	41	31	34	27	36	8	3	24	45	52	33	39	37	21	29	6	6
Performance Appraisal of Staff	25	47	46	85	33	39	29	30	8	5	26	34	35	55	40	41	32	12	10	5
Strategic Planning for College/ University Dev.	33	33	35	40	111	33	25	22	4	8	26	30	41	34	61	36	22	16	11	6
Special attention to College/University Academic Dev.	24	35	31	38	40	98	33	21	6	6	31	31	24	26	34	57	47	22	7	10
Institutional Research	17	24	28	40	35	37	100	27	10	9	15	30	33	37	21	29	66	35	8	7
Compliance of council requirement	22	32	22	30	27	34	49	87	9	7	19	31	22	29	23	24	39	70	8	9
Students welfare	32	23	18	23	12	20	43	56	32	13	25	24	21	31	15	21	41	50	16	13
General Administration & Discipline	49	9	21	29	11	15	26	47	14	36	34	9	24	36	8	13	32	51	11	22
Kendall W = 0.262										Kendall W = 0.302										

Table 4.12: Gender wise ranking by respondents towards factors influencing their current role

Factors influencing current role.	Male										Female									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Role of the Government (and its agencies)	24	24	4	17	7	6	4	6	4	15	20	19	10	18	8	4	4	4	1	10
Council Regulations and guidelines	14	26	11	10	12	8	8	4	13	5	11	27	4	17	12	10	5	3	4	5
Growing competition (Local and International)	12	9	23	20	8	8	7	12	6	6	11	11	19	9	10	10	6	11	5	6
Finding and retaining high quality staff	3	7	11	22	15	15	21	8	4	4	7	8	16	14	9	15	9	6	6	8
Financial Management	6	3	8	9	25	22	8	14	7	8	7	7	10	10	17	14	6	13	3	11
Maintaining specific institutional Image	5	8	7	7	18	29	11	6	9	11	5	6	12	5	11	23	12	9	8	7
Administrative pressure from sponsoring trust	5	7	8	14	9	6	27	18	11	5	8	4	9	11	9	7	21	16	8	5
Increased student diversity	4	3	19	5	7	7	10	27	16	12	9	6	8	3	8	5	15	17	19	8
Pressure of completing enrollment/admissions	13	19	9	5	4	4	10	9	26	13	6	8	5	6	9	8	8	14	26	8
Declining quality of academic and research	24	4	10	2	6	6	5	7	15	32	14	2	5	5	5	2	12	5	18	30
Kendall W=0.007										Kendall W=0.001										

Table 4.13: Gender-wise responses for factors supporting leadership development.

Factors supporting leadership role	Male										Female									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Completing a tertiary qualification relevant to leadership	28	15	4	3	16	8	6	6	9	16	21	14	1	4	19	11	2	4	9	13
Participating higher education leadership seminars	8	26	13	4	16	5	8	11	13	7	5	24	5	6	8	10	8	15	12	5
Accessing leadership information on internet.	10	15	15	13	6	8	11	15	15	3	5	7	12	7	14	8	15	16	8	6
Completing formal leadership program	6	9	14	27	8	9	17	6	6	9	4	5	5	14	14	13	12	13	12	6
Participating in the quality assurance activities of the college/university	7	5	5	10	27	21	10	12	7	7	6	8	10	8	15	10	17	8	11	5
Undertaking self-guided reading on leadership	7	5	11	8	19	27	11	12	7	4	6	6	7	12	15	17	6	9	13	7
Involvement of professional leadership groups	3	8	10	18	6	13	26	7	11	9	10	8	15	16	6	7	16	2	13	5
Learning opportunities during peer group discussion	9	10	16	13	5	8	9	27	8	6	12	9	11	12	5	6	10	19	2	12
Attending learning and teaching conference	13	16	8	9	4	6	11	9	21	14	6	16	12	10	1	7	10	7	12	17
Being involved in informal coaching	20	2	15	6	4	6	2	6	14	36	23	1	20	9	1	9	2	5	6	22
	Kendall W = 0.004										Kendall W = 0.007									

Table 4.14: Gender-wise responses for challenges / hurdles in academic improvement

Challenges in academic improvement	Male										Female									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Management/ Government policies	36	16	7	15	4	5	10	10	12	24	31	15	9	13	2	9	2	10	8	19
Lack of timely and sufficient financial assistance	10	34	11	13	9	6	10	11	24	6	9	19	25	11	5	10	6	9	15	7
Frequently changing guidelines by regulatory authorities	9	8	29	12	8	14	18	21	15	8	4	10	24	17	16	8	16	10	11	4
Difficulty in getting/ retaining/ managing teaching staff	7	8	12	27	10	10	26	8	17	13	7	9	8	20	12	14	22	11	15	10
Multiple Reporting protocols	11	5	10	13	31	20	13	6	14	9	10	11	9	2	21	14	18	9	17	7
Time consumed by non- academic activities	2	8	8	9	22	31	17	12	10	10	10	7	4	6	19	22	24	3	17	7
Students activities affecting academics	7	4	11	16	8	9	58	17	17	10	4	9	4	12	10	12	40	15	14	7
Local political issues	10	8	15	2	5	4	25	49	27	11	6	5	12	6	7	3	21	37	28	9
Difficulties in promoting quality research	6	12	6	2	9	7	9	28	51	33	9	9	2	7	4	4	14	33	38	26
Difficulties in attracting foreign university collaborations	13	8	2	2	5	5	12	36	11	74	8	4	1	4	2	2	8	34	8	75
Kendall W = 0.126										Kendall W = 0.144										

4.7.1 Gender and Leadership Capabilities for effective performance.

In the past few years, women have increasingly expressed their desire to develop their careers, while the percentage of working women has also increased. At the same time, there have been favourable changes with regard to their presence in domains in which, till not long ago, women were accessing with difficulty. Leadership is contextual, as people's individual and organizational characteristics lead to particular perceptions and behaviors. ^[139] Table 4.10, presents the perceptions of male and female academic leaders of present study in the form of ranking on Leadership Capabilities for effective performance in their current role. It is seen from table that there is same trend of ranking for personal leadership capabilities by male and female. Both have assigned first rank to understanding personal strengths and limitations and fifth rank to bouncing back from adversity. Hence, there are no gender differences in the perception of academic leaders in personal leadership capabilities. Kendal W for perceptions of male is 0.128 and for female it is 0.189 showing less disagreement in the perceptions by both genders.

The perceptions of both the genders on Interpersonal Leadership Capabilities are also same as that of personal leadership capabilities. Both male and females gave first ranking to being transparent and honest in dealing with others and fifth ranking to empathizing and working positively with staff. The Kendal W for perceptions is 0.076 and 0.058 for male and female respectively showing less disagreement among both the genders.

The gender based variations in the perceptions of Intellectual leadership Capabilities are also negligible as seen from table 4.10. Both male and females have ranked thinking creatively and laterally at the first level and assessing the likely outcome of course of action at the fifth level. All other parameters are ranked in the same sequence by both male and female with Kendall W 0.097 and 0.181 respectively.

The perception ranking continued for Skills as a leadership capability with both the genders ranked the given parameters in the same ranking. The skill to implement a new educational program effectively and skills of resource management were given first and fifth rank respectively by both male and female. The Kendall W

is 0.022 and 0.032 for male and female perceptions respectively showing led degree of agreement in the perceptions.

4.7.2 Gender and Major Areas of Focus in current role of academic leaders.

An attempt is being made to discuss the variations in the opinion of opposite genders at the academic positions on major areas of focus in the current role they are performing.

Comparing male and female leaders is a continuous evolving situation. Female specific principles and characteristics like using their intuition in the decision making process, being careful, getting a good work-life balance, and social responsibility are the contributing factors for their leadership qualities. Tuning with the basic cultural hypotheses drives the way for men and women thinking and action. ^[140] Hence, the efforts were made to identify the perception differences in the academic leaders of opposite genders based on the decision making capacity of male and female. The main thought behind this was the gender differences changes the way things are executed. Table 4.11 presents the ranking given by male and female for different areas of focus while delivering their portfolio. The ranking was based on 1 to 10, 1 being most important and 10 being least important.

No major differences in the perception by male and female were reported in the major areas of focus in the current role of academic leaders. All male and female ranked Managing Relationship with staff at top, however the major difference here is general administration & discipline was ranked at top by male and it was ranked at eighth place by female. All other parameters under this category for major areas of focus were ranked in the same rank by both the genders. The Kendall W for male was 0.262 and for female it was 0.302 showing less disagreement among the respondents.

The successful academic leaders are those who focuses and prioritize the areas of work. Although studies have reported that gender has some role to play in executing the leadership style, present study do not demonstrate that phenomenon. It is reported that, successful leadership are patterned by gender in two way, in first way women and men who are effective leaders are expected to demonstrate different behaviors and leadership styles, and in second way male and female leaders' assessments differ as to what it means to be successful in their roles. ^[141, 142]

4.7.3 Gender and the factors influencing academic leadership role.

It has been observed that the issues related to gender and leadership are uniform among all countries. ^[143] All the countries are following the same phenomenon and many researchers have studied this aspect across the world. It is reported that despite the feminization of universities in terms of their student intake, ^[144, 145] formal positions of academic leadership in higher education remain concentrated in male hands. Although this phenomenon is changing in modern days it becomes essential to understand whether increasing women representation in the leadership role especially in academic institutes has any different leadership style which influences their role.

Gender wise ranking by respondents towards factors influencing their current role is presented in table 4.12. The results have not shown any major differences in the perceptions of opposite genders in the present study. However, small variations in the perceptions which are reported for some parameters are obvious as they are not significant.

Role of the Government (and its agencies) was ranked at the top by both male and female. Both the genders had perceived that these two factors act as a major influencing factors in academic leadership role. However, interestingly declining quality of academic and research was perceived as least important influencing parameter for academic leadership role. All other parameters including Council Regulations and guidelines , Growing competition (Local and International) , Finding and retaining high quality staff , Financial Management, Maintaining specific institutional Image, Administrative pressure from sponsoring trust, Increased student diversity and Pressure of completing enrollment/admissions were given same rank by both genders. Kendal W was 0.007 for male and 0.001 for females showing less agreement among the respondents.

Although earlier researchers have reported that, underrepresentation of women was the main cause for inadequate knowledge about the characteristics and experiences of effective female leaders in higher education, but the recent time there is significant increases in their numbers. ^[146] In similar way, the influential factors of leadership role are also under reported. But the present study doesn't show any gender variations in the way the influential factors are perceived by male and female.

4.7.4 Gender and the factors supporting academic leadership role.

The gender difference in the leadership style and perception on various factors supporting leadership have been document and established by many researchers. The women are also perceived to better than men regarding honesty and ethical practices and they also have a slight advantage than men when it comes to working to improve the quality of life. ^[147]

Table 4.13 presents gender-wise responses for factors supporting leadership development. These are the rankings given by male and female based on their perceptions on factors supporting academic leadership role from the present study. Completing a tertiary qualification relevant to leadership was given top priority by both the genders however, Being involved in informal coaching was perceived as one of the most important factor for supporting academic leadership role by females on the other hand, this was perceived as least important by males as they have given 10th rank to this factor. This could be because of the fact that women are believing more towards formal coaching than men. The participants were not able to opine as to what is importance of accessing leadership information on internet in supporting academic leadership role. Hence, it was given four different ranks by the equal respondents i.e. 15. All other parameters including participating higher education leadership seminars, accessing leadership information on internet, completing formal leadership program, participating in the quality assurance activities of the college/university, undertaking self-guided reading on leadership, involvement of professional leadership groups, learning opportunities during peer group discussion and attending learning and teaching conference were given same ranking by males and females. The Kendall W for male and female was 0.004 and 0.007 respectively.

The study outcomes are in agreement with the data published in a report “Women and Leadership: Public Says Women are Equally Qualified, but Barriers Persist” ^[147] where it is reported that men and women tend to agree on the relative importance of the top tier of leadership traits. Larger gender gaps emerge on some of the less important traits. As per the public opinion there is minor difference between men and women on several of these leadership characters. As per the majority public opinion when it comes to intelligence and innovation, men and women display those qualities equally. ^[147]

4.7.5 Gender and challenges / hurdles in academic improvement.

Leadership for women has been viewed as a complicated business. Historically, women have limited representation in leadership positions in corporate and educational positions. Earlier studies demonstrated that gender barriers, discrimination, and a late entrance into the workforce and academia are the causes responsible for underrepresentation of women in higher education leadership. ^[148, 149, 150] These reasons may contribute to the differences in the perceptions by the male and female.

The perceptions on the challenges/hurdles in academic improvement by male and female are presented in table 4.14. It is seen from that table that most of the male and female perceived management/Government policies as an important challenge in academic improvement of an institute and it was ranked 1 in the study. Lack of timely and sufficient financial assistance was perceived as a second important challenge by the male however female perceived this as a third important challenge in academic improvement of the institute. Attracting foreign universities was not given importance in terms of academic improvement by male and female as it might have not considered important in the current setup of the Indian higher education. It was given last ranking by the respondents. There was similar opinion by male and female on all other parameters including frequently changing guidelines by regulatory authorities, difficulty in getting/ retaining/ managing teaching staff, multiple reporting protocols, time consumed by non-academic activities, students activities affecting academics, local political issues and difficulties in promoting quality research. The Kendall W was 0.126 and 0.144 for male and female respectively showing less agreement in perceptions.

Hence, it is clear from above discussion that male and female are not showing major variations in the perceptions on major challenges in the academic improvements. This supports the fact that Indian higher education institutions give similar opportunities to both the genders to work and there are no gender specific challenges for the academic leaders. Eagly and Carli ^[151] described the evolving structure of the workplace. Women no longer encounter a glass ceiling in pursuing leadership positions. According to Vinkenbunrg *et.al.*, ^[152] gender expectations impact

leadership perception and promotion. But present results are in contradictory to what is reported by other researchers as there are no variations in the perceptions by men and women.

4.8 Academic qualification wise perceptions of academic leaders on various aspects of academic leadership.

All nations across the world has their own ideology of life, and this becomes a basis to run the educational system of the country. An academic leader is responsible for assurance of effective educational process. ^[127] Leading always influences others to act to complete definite objectives and the method a person handles himself is called style. Principal is center of all the educational exertions and therefore he has to play the multiple roles like organizer, leader, governor, business director, coordinator, teacher, guide, philosopher and friend. ^[153] Yukl ^[154] has stated leadership as act of influencing juniors to accomplish organizational goals through authority. With these references, the leader has to be very much dynamic and influential while delivering his portfolio. The effective capabilities of the leader are always earned through learning and practicing. The process of learning has always a strong role to play in the leadership development. Hence, the qualification earned by the academic leader during the process of learning decides how the leader perceives importance of different leadership aspect in the existing academic framework.

The results of academic qualification wise perceptions of academic leaders on various aspects of academic leadership are presented in table 4.15 to 4.19. For better interpretation, discussion and understanding the topic 5.8 is further divided into five subsections as mentioned below.

- 4.8.1- Academic qualification and Leadership Capabilities for effective performance.
- 4.8.2- Academic qualification and Major Areas of Focus in current role of academic leaders.
- 4.8.3- Academic qualification and the factors influencing academic leadership role.
- 4.8.4- Academic qualification and the factors supporting academic leadership role.
- 4.8.5- Academic qualification and challenges / hurdles in academic improvement.

In present study, 144 of 687 i.e. 21 % academic leaders were Ph.D. qualified and 79 % were holding one of the post graduate degree including M.Sc./MD/MS/

DNB/DM/MCH/MDS. In the subsequent discussion, the emphasis is given to discuss and support any variations in the perceptions of academic leaders based on their qualification.

Table 4.15: Academic Qualification wise rankings by the participants for various leadership capabilities for effective performance in the current role of academic leaders.

Leadership Capabilities		Ranking by leaders with M.Sc./MD/MS/DNB/DM/ MCH/MDS qualification					Ranking by leaders with Ph.D qualification				
		1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
Personal Capabilities	Understanding personal strengths and limitations	179	122	101	61	80	42	21	28	18	35
	Being Confident	117	179	127	99	21	30	45	31	31	7
	Taking Responsibilities	110	111	218	72	32	27	34	57	21	5
	Wanting to achieve the best outcome possible	67	101	65	234	76	26	33	14	53	18
	Bouncing back from adversity	70	30	32	77	334	19	11	14	21	79
Kendall W = 0.178						Kendall W = 0.078					
Interpersonal Capabilities	Being transparent and honest in dealing with others	238	70	77	65	93	58	17	18	20	31
	Motivating others to achieve goals	90	165	96	134	58	26	47	34	25	12
	Developing and contributing positively in team based programs	73	112	186	108	64	13	32	53	28	18
	Listening to different point of views before coming to decision	51	126	110	155	101	23	28	23	42	28
	Empathizing and working positively with staff	91	70	74	81	227	24	20	16	29	55
Kendall W = 0.072						Kendall W = 0.052					
Intellectual Capabilities	Thinking creatively and laterally	184	177	51	51	80	49	46	18	9	22
	Setting and justifying priorities of work	141	163	83	98	58	34	48	18	31	13
	Making sense of	77	83	221	103	59	19	15	73	23	14

	learning from experiences										
	Adjusting plan of action in response to the problems encountered while implementing.	59	77	104	205	98	18	27	19	51	29
	Assessing the likely outcome of course of action.	82	43	84	86	248	24	8	16	30	66
		Kendall W = 0.131					Kendall W = 0.137				
Skills	Skill to implement a new educational program effectively	197	92	75	61	118	48	21	20	22	33
	Being able to use Information Communication technology	103	144	93	126	77	21	40	29	29	25
	Ability to chair meetings effectively	87	106	171	92	87	19	27	44	33	21
	Ability to develop policy documents	70	123	101	161	88	26	30	25	41	22
	Skills of resource management.	86	78	103	103	173	30	26	26	19	43
		Kendall W = 0.034					Kendall W = 0.007				

Table 4.16: Academic qualification wise rankings by the participants for major areas of focus in their current role

Major areas of focus	M.Sc./MD/MS/DNB/DM/MCH/MDS										Ph.D.									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Managing Relationship with staff	142	31	57	25	60	46	14	29	25	22	41	11	14	2	17	8	11	8	1	4
Staff Development	53	125	60	41	57	49	23	34	14	17	16	41	11	12	12	16	7	5	0	0
College/University Development	49	70	106	59	56	59	39	49	12	9	8	17	38	15	14	12	9	16	2	0
Performance Appraisal of Staff	45	64	62	108	60	63	51	31	16	8	6	17	19	32	13	17	10	11	2	2
Strategic Planning for College/ University Dev.	45	48	61	57	130	56	39	31	13	14	14	15	15	17	42	13	8	7	2	0
Special attention to College/University Academic Dev.	44	53	47	49	58	114	62	38	12	14	11	13	8	15	16	41	18	5	1	2
Institutional Research	23	48	52	56	46	52	129	52	14	14	9	6	9	21	10	14	37	10	4	2
Compliance of council requirement	36	53	31	50	36	48	68	121	12	14	5	10	13	9	14	10	20	36	5	2
Students welfare	48	35	28	46	23	36	69	80	37	19	9	12	11	8	4	5	15	26	11	7
General Administration & Discipline	58	16	39	52	17	20	49	78	20	44	25	2	6	13	2	8	9	20	5	14
Kendall W = 0.277										Kendall W = 0.297										

Table 4.17: Academic qualification wise responses for factors influencing their current role

Factors influencing current role.	M.Sc./MD/MS/DNB/DM/MCH/MDS										Ph.D.									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Role of the Government (and its agencies)	39	34	10	29	14	8	8	10	4	20	5	9	4	6	1	2	0	0	1	5
Council Regulations and guidelines	18	44	13	22	21	15	12	6	15	10	7	9	2	5	3	3	1	1	2	0
Growing competition (Local and International)	21	18	33	25	15	14	10	20	10	10	2	2	9	4	3	4	3	3	1	2
Finding and retaining high quality staff	8	13	22	29	20	27	27	12	7	10	2	2	5	7	4	3	3	2	3	2
Financial Management	11	6	18	17	33	32	12	20	10	16	2	4	0	2	9	4	2	7	0	3
Maintaining specific institutional Image	7	11	15	11	27	44	19	10	16	16	3	3	4	1	2	8	4	5	1	2
Administrative pressure from sponsoring trust	11	10	15	23	15	9	36	32	14	10	2	1	2	2	3	4	12	2	5	0
Increased student diversity	9	8	26	7	11	11	22	35	30	16	4	1	1	1	4	1	3	9	5	4
Pressure of completing enrollment/admissions	16	25	12	8	10	8	15	19	46	18	3	2	2	3	3	4	3	4	6	3
Declining quality of academic and research	35	6	11	5	10	8	15	12	24	50	3	0	4	2	1	0	2	0	9	12
Kendall W=0.009											Kendall W=0.009									

Table 4.18: Academic qualification wise responses for factors supporting leadership development

Factors supporting leadership role	M.Sc./MD/MS/DNB/DM/MCH/MDS										Ph.D.									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Completing a tertiary qualification relevant to leadership	42	23	5	7	28	16	8	8	14	25	7	6	0	0	7	3	0	2	4	4
Participating higher education leadership seminars	11	40	15	10	20	11	14	23	22	10	2	10	3	0	4	4	2	3	3	2
Accessing leadership information on internet.	12	19	21	16	19	15	22	26	19	7	3	3	6	4	1	1	4	5	4	2
Completing formal leadership program	7	13	15	34	17	20	25	15	16	14	3	1	4	7	5	2	4	4	2	1
Participating in the quality assurance activities of the college/university	11	10	13	17	33	26	23	19	17	7	2	3	2	1	9	5	4	1	1	5
Undertaking self-guided reading on leadership	9	10	18	15	30	33	16	17	18	10	4	1	0	5	4	11	1	4	2	1
Involvement of professional leadership groups	10	13	23	29	11	20	30	8	18	14	3	3	2	5	1	0	12	1	6	0
Learning opportunities during peer group discussion	19	17	23	20	8	12	18	35	9	15	2	2	4	5	2	2	1	11	1	3
Attending learning and teaching conference	17	28	18	14	5	9	17	15	25	28	2	4	2	5	0	4	4	1	8	3
Being involved in informal coaching	38	3	25	14	5	14	3	10	18	46	5	0	10	1	0	1	1	1	2	12
Kendall W = 0.004											Kendall W = 0.005									

Table 4.19: Academic qualification wise responses towards challenges / hurdles in academic improvement

Challenges in academic improvement	M.Sc./MD/MS/DNB/DM/MCH/MDS										Ph.D.									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Management/ Government policies	54	28	14	23	5	13	10	17	15	32	13	3	2	5	1	1	2	3	5	11
Lack of timely and sufficient financial assistance	16	45	28	23	12	11	14	17	30	10	3	8	8	1	2	5	2	3	9	3
Frequently changing guidelines by regulatory authorities	11	16	43	26	19	19	25	25	20	11	2	2	10	3	5	3	9	6	6	1
Difficulty in getting/ retaining/ managing teaching staff	13	12	19	35	21	22	37	13	26	21	1	5	1	12	1	2	11	6	6	2
Multiple Reporting protocols	18	14	18	12	44	30	22	10	22	14	3	2	1	3	8	4	9	5	9	2
Time consumed by non-academic activities	10	12	9	15	34	45	32	11	24	13	2	3	3	0	7	8	9	4	3	4
Students activities affecting academics	9	10	13	24	14	16	78	29	24	15	2	3	2	4	4	5	20	3	7	2
Local political issues	12	11	22	7	9	6	40	64	51	15	4	2	5	1	3	1	6	22	4	5
Difficulties in promoting quality research	14	19	7	6	13	9	16	51	66	46	1	2	1	3	0	2	7	10	23	13
Difficulties in attracting foreign university collaborations	19	9	3	5	5	5	18	55	14	115	2	3	0	1	2	2	2	15	5	34
Kendall W = 0.123											Kendall W = 0.179									

4.8.1 Academic qualification and Leadership Capabilities for effective performance.

In the general perception of the academician it is perceived that, if the leaders are qualified with highest academic qualifications like Ph.D., they will have less challenges while executing their role as compare to the leaders with mere post graduate degree. In the study conducted by Chua *et.al.* ^[155] on the factors of leadership skills of secondary school principals in five states of Malaysia they have emphasized that as academic qualification was found as a significant factor of principal leadership skill, government education authority should support with more opportunities for the school leaders to further their studies particularly in the field of educational leadership, especially at the level of master and Ph.D. degrees, because. ^[155] The importance of doctoral level qualification has been emphasized by many other researchers thinking that it will help the academic leader to execute their role.

The results of the academic qualification wise rankings by the participants for various leadership capabilities for effective performance in the current role of academic leaders are presented in table 4.15. It is seen from the results that respondents with post-graduate and doctoral qualification have ranked Understanding personal strengths and limitations under personal capabilities at rank 1, however Bouncing back from adversity was ranked at fifth number. All other parameters under Personal Capabilities were ranked equally by both groups. The Kendal W was 0.178 and 0.078 for respondents with postgraduate qualification and doctoral qualification respectively showing less agreement among the respondents.

Similarly, under the Interpersonal Capabilities Being transparent and honest in dealing with others was ranked at top however Empathizing and working positively with staff was ranked at fifth number by both groups with Kendall W 0.072 for respondents with post graduate qualification and Kendall W 0.052 for respondents with doctoral qualification. Hence, under the interpersonal capabilities the respondents have less agreement as shown by Kendall W values.

Similar results have been reported under Intellectual Capabilities and skill capabilities of academic leaders for effective performance in health sciences institutions. The Kendal W values for both these capabilities shows less agreement among the respondents. Hence, it is evident from above discussion that, all academic

leaders of the present study perceived that, educational qualification of the academic leader does not matter when it comes to the decision of what is important for academic leader under personal, interpersonal, intellectual and skill capabilities for effective performance in the current role of academic leaders. Therefore, finding of the present study support the findings by Hughes, ^[156] who reports no association between perceived leadership style and level of education.

4.8.2 Academic qualification and Major Areas of Focus in current role of academic leaders.

The experience of the academic leaders based on their qualifications helps in decision making. The general perception says that highly qualified leaders tend to lead with dynamic leadership which is important for effective performance of health sciences institutes. Great leaders possess a trait or characteristic that creates an innate ability to lead. ^[157] Effective leaders are vitally important to higher education as they define an institution and its practices. ^[158] Furthermore, good leaders are confident in their judgment, and they hold themselves and their followers to high expectations. ^[159]

The results of academic qualification wise rankings by the participants for major areas of focus in their current role are presented in table 4.16. The perceptions of the academic leaders were sought on 10 selected focus areas and ranking on the scale of 1 to 10 based on its importance. It is seen from the results that, Managing Relationship with staff was perceived as most important area of focus by both groups. However, General Administration & Discipline was perceived as least important factor to focus in their current role by leaders with post graduate qualification however it was perceived as most important focus area by leaders with doctoral qualification. This was the major variation reported in this section. All other parameter of major areas of focus in current role for effective performance including Staff Development, College/University Development, Performance Appraisal of Staff, Strategic Planning for College/ University Dev., Special attention to College/University Academic Dev., Institutional Research, Compliance of council requirement and Students welfare were given same rank by both the groups. The Kendall W was 0.277 for leaders with post graduate qualification and it was 0.297 for the leaders with doctoral qualification showing less agreement among the respondents.

Hence, it is evident from the discussion that the qualifications essentially has no impact on the perception of academic leaders on the major areas of focus. If the same perceptions lead to action there will be no difference in the efficiency of academic leaders, In this case the findings are not matching with previous study in which Khan ^[160] explored that the heads with higher professional qualifications are more efficient.

4.8.3 Academic qualification and the factors influencing academic leadership role.

It is common belief that age and experience may play very vital role in leadership behavior besides professional and academic knowledge of academic leader. There is a myth in most of the cultures that as people get elder they become wiser due more exposure and experience. ^[127] The way in which leader plays his role either as principal or leader, shapes how he/she thinks, acts and feels in the school ^[153] when he is in the process of acquiring the qualification.

With those reference the perceptions about the factors influencing the delivery of leader's role may be dependent on the qualification of the academic leader. With this perception an attempt was made to study the relation between the qualification of the academic leaders and variations on the perceptions on factors influencing current academic role.

The results of academic qualification wise responses for factors influencing current role of academic leaders are presented in table 4.17. It is seen from the table that, Role of the Government (and its agencies) was given first rank by leaders with post graduate qualification, however this was given second rank by leaders with doctoral qualification. There was no variation in the perceptions of acidic leaders as declining quality of academic and research was given last rank by both the groups. All other parameters including Growing competition (Local and International), Finding and retaining high quality staff, Financial Management, Maintaining specific institutional Image, Administrative pressure from sponsoring trust, Increased student diversity and Pressure of completing enrollment/admissions were given similar ranks by both the groups. The Kendall W for respondents with post graduate degree as well as doctoral degree was 0.009 showing less agreement among the respondents on the perceptions on factors influencing current role.

Cagle ^[161] has regarded age, experience, education, and size of the institution as factor of leadership style. Katozai ^[162] argued that knowledge is a chief weapon in the hand of principal and therefore he/she should be a qualified man. The researchers in earlier studies believed that, educational qualification is vital in executing leadership role. However, present study have shown that there are no differences in the perception leading to leadership styles among differently qualified academic leaders. Hence the study results are contradictory to earlier reports by Cagle ^[161] and Katozai ^[162].

4.8.4 Academic qualification and the factors supporting academic leadership role.

The value of appropriately skilled and trained educators for the success of the education was documented by Lenyai. ^[163] Similarly, since quality in education retracts from effective leadership, the quest for quality in education necessitates that principals be up-to-date with developments in the education and training fields. ^[164] In the light of the preceding statement, Jones *et.al.* ^[165] regard programmes for professional development [for principals] as the oxygen that ensures that principals survive as educated and trained professionals. These skills and training to the academic leaders comes with several supporting factors for leadership development. Hence, an attempt was made to understand relation between perceptions of academic leaders and academic qualification they possesses.

The results of academic qualification wise responses for factors supporting leadership development are presented in table 4.18. It is seen from the results that completing a tertiary qualification relevant to leadership was perceived as most important factor in supporting the academic leadership by both the groups with post-graduate and doctoral qualification. Being involved in informal coaching was placed at last rank by both the groups. All other parameters under study including participating higher education leadership seminars, accessing leadership information on internet, completing formal leadership program, participating in the quality assurance activities of the college/university, undertaking self-guided reading on leadership, involvement of professional leadership groups, learning opportunities during peer group discussion and attending learning and teaching conference were given somewhat similar ranks by both the groups. No major variation was reported in the opinion of the leaders with post graduate and doctoral qualification. Kendall W for

leaders with post graduate degree was 0.004, and it was 0.005 for leaders with doctoral degree showing less agreement among the respondents.

Anderson ^[166] stated that the quality of accomplishment of any organization is related to the nature of its leadership, and education is no exception. Leadership is basic element of educational administration, the term describes the relation between persons, where one person affects another person or group in such a way that common direction is given to their efforts. ^[167] Stogdill ^[168] thought of leadership to be working relationship among members of a group, where the leader acquires status through active participation and demonstration of his capacity for carrying co-operative tasks through co-operation, the strength of educational system and the contribution. In order to acquire those qualities for academic leadership, education and qualification seems to be important. There are supporting factors for leadership development as well. But present study is contradictory to above studies as there are no perception differences among the leaders with different academic qualifications.

4.8.5 Academic qualification and challenges / hurdles in academic improvement.

Education is a composite particular field and its well-organized technical competency, administrative ability and an understanding of educational development. On the professional side the educational administrator must be familiar with the specialized skills required in education, knowledge needed for sound curriculum development and accurate evaluation of teachers and students and have an intimate knowledge of process of the educational system. ^[167] However, it is often seen that, in the process of gaining knowledge the leaders face several challenges from within and outside the academic setup. Earlier researchers have also emphasized that, good leaders must be enthusiastic about their work and the potential of the institutions that employ them. ^[169] But this enthusiasm many times is compromised because of the challenges and hurdles those affect the leadership development. Hence, an attempt is being made to understand the qualification level and the variations in the perception of academic leaders.

Table 4.19 illustrates academic qualification wise responses towards challenges / hurdles in academic improvement. It is seen from table that, management/ Government policies was perceived as a major challenge by both the groups and it was ranked at the top. However, difficulties in attracting foreign

university collaborations was least important challenge by both the groups and it was placed at the end by both the groups. There are no major variations in the perceptions of academic leaders with different qualification in present study except the factors like difficulty in getting/ retaining/ managing teaching staff were ranked at different level by both groups. However, all other factors under study including Lack of timely and sufficient financial assistance, frequently changing guidelines by regulatory authorities, difficulty in getting/ retaining/ managing teaching staff, multiple reporting protocol, time consumed by non-academic activities, students activities affecting academics, local political issues, difficulties in promoting quality research etc. were ranked almost at same level by the academic leaders with post graduate and doctoral qualification with Kendall W 0.123 and 0.179 showing less agreement among them.

Hence, it is observed from above discussion that there are no variations in the perception level among the leaders with different qualification when it comes to the hurdles/challenges. This could be due to the reason that, the leaders in present academic setup are more adaptive to the existing situation and their main focus is on development rather than attention towards the challenges. The researchers earlier have reported that, adaptive leaders, also known as transformational leaders, ^[170] work with followers to enhance performance and generate creative solutions to complex problems. ^[170, 171, 172, 173] and due to these reasons the perceptions of the academic leaders with different academic qualification might be same.

5.1 Conclusion

The main focus of the research was to understand the perception of academic leaders about various leadership qualities in various health sciences institutes. In a broader perspective, it is seen that the academic leaders of the health sciences institutes have better understanding about the leadership capabilities required for effective performance of health sciences institutions. Hence, on the basis of the results achieved and subsequent discussion in the previous chapter, following conclusions are drawn from the study.

- i. Perceptions of academic leaders on leadership capabilities revealed that, understanding personal strengths and limitations is most important personal capability, being transparent and honest in dealing with others is most important Interpersonal Capability and thinking creatively and laterally is important among Intellectual Capabilities, however under the Skill set to implement a new educational program effectively is most important skill for academic leaders.
- ii. The major areas of focus in the current role as perceived by academic leaders are managing the relationship with the staff, Staff Development and College/University Development.
- iii. The major factors influencing academic leadership role as perceived by academic leaders are Role of the Government (and its agencies), Council Regulations and guidelines and Growing competition (Local and International).
- iv. As perceived by the academic leader's factors supporting leadership development are completing a tertiary qualification relevant to leadership, participating higher education leadership seminars and accessing leadership information on internet.
- v. Challenges in academic improvement of institute for effective performance as perceived by academic leaders are Management/ Government policies, Lack of timely and sufficient financial assistance and frequently changing guidelines by regulatory authorities.

- vi. There was no variation in the perceptions by male and female academic leaders for the given parameters viz. Leadership Capabilities for effective performance, Major Areas of Focus in current role of academic leaders, factors influencing academic leadership role, factors supporting academic leadership role, challenges / hurdles in academic improvement.
- vii. There was no association between level of education and perceived leadership style, major areas of focus, factors influencing/supporting academic leadership role and the challenges in academic improvement.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the outcomes of the study, following recommendations are made.

- i. The study recommends that there is need to bring out an extensive leadership development program in the academics and especially health sciences institutions.
- ii. Institutional research has not been regarded as important or major area of focus by the academic leaders, this needs to be address through the formal leadership program for the academic leaders.
- iii. Role of the Government (and its agencies) as well as Council Regulations and guidelines are perceived as major influential parameters in performing current leadership role. Hence, the apex council for respective higher educational branch need to understand the limitation of the higher educational institutes and accordingly prepare the guidelines for execution of academic program.
- iv. Central and state governments should put a check on frequently changing policies which are affecting the academic institutes and timely and sufficient financial assistance for the higher educational institutes needs to be ensured for productive outcome from the academics.

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APENDIX A

DATA COLLECTION TOOL

Perceptions of Academic Leaders on various aspects of Academic Leadership for Effective Performance of Health Sciences Institutes

Note:

- (1) This is online survey. You are requested to complete the same and it will not take more than 35 minutes to complete it.*
- (2) Please fill-up the consent form in Part-A, personal details in Part-B, think on questions and choose appropriate response in Part-C.*
- (3) When you have completed all the parts, just click on the submit button on the final page of survey.*
- (4) If you have any query, please call the principal investigator Dr. Kalidas Dattatraya Chavan on 7720036370 or email kdchavan17@gmail.com*

Part A

CONSENT

I have been fully understood the various aspects of the study entitled: **“Perceptions of Academic Leaders on various aspects of Academic Leadership for Effective Performance of Health Sciences Institutes”**

1. I hereby voluntarily consent to participate in the study.
2. I have received information of the nature, purpose, duration and expected effects of the study and what I will be expected to do.
3. I understand that my participation in the study is voluntary and that I may refuse to participate or may withdraw from the study anytime.
4. I understand that my identity will not be revealed in any publication.
5. I voluntary agree to take part in the above study.

Name:

Date:

Place:

PART B
PERSONAL DETAILS

<i>Sr.No.</i>	<i>Details</i>	<i>Particulars</i>	<i>Options</i>
1	<i>Name</i>		
2	<i>Age</i>		
3	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Male</i>	1
		<i>Female</i>	2
4	<i>Academic Qualification</i>	<i>M.Sc./MD/MS/DNB/DM/MCH/MDS</i>	1
		<i>Ph.D.</i>	2
		<i>Post Doc.</i>	3
		<i>Any other</i>	4
5	<i>Disciplinary Background</i>	<i>Modern Medicine</i>	1
		<i>Dentistry</i>	2
		<i>Ayurveda</i>	3
		<i>Homoeopathy</i>	4
		<i>Nursing</i>	5
		<i>Siddha</i>	6
		<i>Unani</i>	7
		<i>Allied Health</i> <i>Any other (pl specify)</i>	8 9
6	<i>Name of the Department</i>		
	<i>Name of the College</i>		
	<i>Name of the University</i>		
7	<i>Leadership Role</i>	<i>Vice Chancellor</i>	1
		<i>Dean/Principal</i>	2
		<i>Head of the department</i>	3
8	<i>How many years have you held your current role?</i>	<i>Under 1 year</i>	1
		<i>1-3 years</i>	2
		<i>4-6 years</i>	3
		<i>7-10 years</i>	4
		<i>More than 10 years</i>	5
9	<i>How many academic and administrative staff reports to you directly?</i>	<i>Less than 10</i>	1
		<i>10-40</i>	2
		<i>41-80</i>	3
		<i>81-120</i>	4
		<i>Above 120</i>	5
10	<i>What was your role prior to your current role?</i>	<i>Director</i>	1
		<i>Dean/Principal</i>	2
		<i>Vice Dean/Principal</i>	3
		<i>Registrar</i>	4
		<i>Professor & Head</i>	5
		<i>Professor</i>	6

<i>Sr.No.</i>	<i>Details</i>	<i>Particulars</i>	<i>Options</i>
		<i>Asso. Professor</i>	<i>7</i>
		<i>Any other (pl specify)</i>	<i>8</i>
<i>10</i>	<i>How many years you were in this prior role?</i>	<i>0-1 years</i>	<i>1</i>
		<i>2-5 years</i>	<i>2</i>
		<i>6-10 years</i>	<i>3</i>
		<i>More than 10 years</i>	<i>4</i>

PART C
QUESTIONNAIRE

Sr. No.	Particulars	Reponses
A	Leadership Capabilities for effective performance. <i>(How important do you believe each of the following capabilities for effective performance in your current role?)</i>	Please assign ranks (1 to 5) in ascending order of importance
I	Personal Capabilities	
1	Understanding personal strengths and limitations	
2	Being Confident	
3	Taking Responsibilities	
4	Wanting to achieve the best outcome possible	
5	Bouncing back from adversity	
II	Interpersonal Capabilities	
1	Being transparent and honest in dealing with others	
2	Motivating others to achieve goals	
3	Developing and contributing positively in team based programs	
4	Listening to different point of views before coming to decision	
5	Empathizing and working positively with staff	
III	Intellectual Capabilities	
1	Thinking creatively and laterally	
2	Setting and justifying priorities of work	
3	Making sense of learning from experiences	
4	Adjusting plan of action in response to the problems encountered while implementing.	
5	Assessing the likely outcome of course of action.	
IV	Skills Proficiency	
1	Skill to implement a new educational program effectively.	
2	Being able to use Information Communication technology	
3	Ability to chair meetings effectively	
4	Ability to develop policy documents	
5	Skills of resource management.	

B	Major areas of Focus in your current role <i>(How Important do you believe each of the following parameters/areas or activities is to delivery of your portfolio)</i>	Please assign ranks (1 to 10) in ascending order of importance
1	Managing the Relationship with the staff	
2	Staff Development	
3	College/University Development	
4	Performance Appraisal of Staff	
5	Strategic Planning for College/University Development	
6	Special attention to College/University Academic Development	
7	Institutional Research	
8	Compliance of council requirement (UGC/NMC/MCI/DCI/INC etc)	
9	Students welfare	
10	General Administration and Discipline	
C	The factors influencing academic leadership role <i>(Please rate the level of impact that each of the following has on your daily work)</i>	Please assign ranks (1 to 10) in ascending order of importance
1	Role of the Government (and its agencies)	
2	Council Regulations and guidelines	
3	Growing competition (Local and International)	
4	Finding and retaining high quality staff	
5	Financial Management	
6	Maintaining specific institutional Image	
7	Administrative pressure from sponsoring body/trust	
8	Increased student diversity	
9	Pressure of completing enrollment/admissions	
10	Declining quality of academic and research	

D	Support for Your Leadership Development <i>(In your experience how effective has each of the following activities been in developing your capabilities as an academic leader?)</i>	Please assign ranks (1 to 10) in ascending order of importance
1	Completing a tertiary qualification relevant to leadership	
2	Participating higher education leadership seminars	
3	Accessing leadership information on internet.	
4	Completing formal leadership program	
5	Participating in the quality assurance activities of the college/university.	
6	Undertaking self-guided reading on leadership.	
7	Involvement of professional leadership groups/associations.	
8	Learning opportunities during peer group discussion.	
9	Attending learning and teaching conference.	
10	Being involved in informal mentoring/coaching.	
E	Challenges in academic improvements of institute for effective performance as perceived by you	Please assign ranks (1 to 10) in ascending order of importance
1	Management/ Government policies	
2	Lack of timely and sufficient financial assistance	
3	Frequently changing guidelines by regulatory authorities	
4	Difficulty in getting/ retaining/ managing teaching staff	
5	Multiple Reporting protocols (to Government / other authorities)	
6	Time consumed by non-academic activities	
7	Students activities affecting academics	
8	Local political issues	
9	Difficulties in promoting quality research	
10	Difficulties in attracting foreign university collaborations	